

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Part I: Salmonellosis

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Objective and Methodology:

In order to design effective public health strategies, and, in particular, effective food safety interventions, to reduce the burden of foodborne disease, the most important sources of enteric illnesses should be identified and ranked. Both retrospective (case-control) and prospective (cohort) observational studies have for long been powerful approaches among epidemiologists to investigate the association or causal effect of exposure and illness. In the literature, there are numerous case-control and cohort studies performed for the investigation of the most important routes of transmission of sporadic foodborne infections. The objective of this systematic review and meta-analysis was to synthesise the associations between foodborne diseases and risk factors by combining results of relevant primary studies. Since primary studies investigated a variety of potential determinants of disease, a categorisation scheme was developed to hierarchically group the risk factors, which included travel, host-specific factors and pathways of exposure – comprising person-to-person, animal, environment and food routes of transmission. In this way, the risk factors as originally labelled in the primary studies underwent a harmonisation that supported the integration and combination of results from all collected studies. The enteric diseases, for which case-control and cohort studies were gathered, were those caused by *Salmonella* spp, *Campylobacter*, Shiga-toxin *Escherichia coli* (STEC), *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, Norovirus, Hepatitis A virus, Hepatitis E virus, *Cryptosporidium* spp. and *Giardia duodenalis*. Systematic searches using a combination of suitable keywords were conducted using the bibliographic engines Science Direct, PubMed, Scielo, ISI Web of Science and Scopus in English, Spanish, French and Portuguese. Primary studies that passed the screening for relevance were marked as having potential for bias if they failed to meet at least one of the methodological quality assessment criteria. After careful data extraction, meta-analyses models were adjusted within appropriate risk factor data partitions in order to estimate overall odds-ratios (OR) extracting variability due to primary studies and type of statistical analysis. Diagnostics based on Cook's distance was assessed for every meta-analysis model in

order to remove any influential OR originated from studies deemed as having some potential for bias.

Results for Salmonella spp.:

The quality assessment stage was passed by 69 primary studies investigating only sporadic salmonellosis, which were conducted between 1987 and 2013. From these, eighteen studies investigated exposures in children and infants, while only one study focused on the immunocompromised population. These primary studies provided 1304 ORs categorised for meta-analysis, being 65% of the meta-analytical data produced by case-control studies from USA (21), UK (10), Germany (6) and Canada (4). Forty-eight case-control studies (65%) employed a matched design and produced a total of 804 matched ORs. Seven-hundred-and-fifty reported ORs were not adjusted by any confounder, while 554 ORs were adjusted by using either Mantel-Haenzel method or logistic regressions. After quality assessment, 15 case-control studies were marked as being below standards, which yielded a total of 207 potentially-biased ORs. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the myriad of pathways of exposure (1117 ORs) than on host specific factors (128) and travel (59).

According to this meta-analysis study, the most important determinants of disease in the children population, in decreasing order are: contact with farm animals (OR=5.98; 95% CI: 2.79 – 12.79); person-to-person transmission (OR=4.00; 95% CI: 1.81 – 8.81); exposure through playground (OR=3.65; 95% CI: 2.22 – 6.00); recent use of anti-acids (OR=3.35; 95% CI: 1.84 – 6.10); attendance to day care centre (OR=3.31; 95% CI: 1.77 – 6.20); drink water (OR=3.25; 95% CI: 1.67 – 6.32); pork meat (OR=3.19; 95% CI: 1.95 – 5.24); contact with pets (OR=3.16; 95% CI: 1.95 – 5.24); contact with wild animals (OR=3.04; 95% CI: 1.69 – 5.48); minced beef (OR=2.78; 95% CI: 1.79 – 4.31); recent use of antibiotics (OR=2.65; 95% CI: 1.81 – 3.87); milk powder in infants (OR=2.30; 95% CI: 1.68 – 5.15); fresh vegetables (overall OR=2.00; 95% CI: 0.80 – 4.96); processed meat (overall OR=1.84; 95% CI: 1.27 – 2.66); any eggs (OR=1.48; 95% CI: 1.17 – 1.89) and chicken meat (OR=1.44; 95% CI: 1.06 – 1.95).

In the mixed population, international travel is as important a risk factor (OR=4.17; 95% CI: 1.71 – 10.13) as the host-specific factors of recent use of antibiotics (OR=5.18; 95% CI: 3.60 – 7.45) and chronic disease (OR=3.60; 95% CI: 2.35 – 5.50). Risk of contagion is also substantial from drinking water (OR=2.99; 95% CI: 1.79 – 3.72); occupational exposure (OR=2.58; 95% CI: 1.79 – 3.71), person-to-person transmission (OR=2.47; 95% CI: 1.19 – 5.14) and recreational water (OR=2.40; 95% CI: 1.33 – 4.36); all of them of greater significance than contact with pet, farm and wild animals (pooled ORs in the range of 1.75 – 1.98). Within the food vehicles of transmission, the highest associations between salmonellosis and food were observed for: egg products (OR=2.90; 95% CI: 1.27 – 6.65); pork meat (OR= 2.66; 95% CI: 2.08 – 3.42); red meats other than beef (OR=2.44; 95% CI: 1.64 – 3.64); any eggs (OR=2.11; 95% CI: 0.95 – 4.64); poultry meat (OR=2.11; 95% CI: 1.69 – 2.62); fast-food (OR=2.07; 95% CI: 1.26 – 3.38); composite fast-food (OR=2.07; 95% CI: 1.26 – 3.38); BBQ meats (OR= 2.06; 95% CI: 0.93 – 4.58); non-RTE composite dishes from restaurants (OR=2.04; 95% CI: 1.26 – 3.28), multi-ingredient sandwiches (OR=1.96; 95% CI: 1.09 – 3.52); processed meat (OR=1.87; 95% CI: 1.48 – 2.34); beef (OR=1.67; 95% CI: 1.27 – 2.15); dairy-based RTE foods (OR=1.41; 95% CI: 0.97 – 2.06); molluscs (OR=1.39; 95% CI: 0.66 – 2.91); beverages (OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.76 – 2.39) and meat-based RTE foods (OR=1.26; 95% CI: 0.87 – 1.82). Foodstuffs that on meta-analysis had weak

(pooled OR marginally higher than one) or non-significant association with salmonellosis in the mixed population were: vegetables, roots, nuts, vegetable products, dairy-origin fats, processed fish, cheese, milk and fish. Other meta-analysis models were adjusted to estimate the effects of food handling (raw, undercooked, unwashed) and setting (home, eating out) on the mean ORs in selected food classes. It was found that people who ate undercooked pork had, on average, 3.769 (95% CI: 2.148 – 6.183) times the odds of becoming infected than those who *simply* ate pork. Eating pork prepared outside the home increased the odds by 3.785 (95% CI: 1.795 – 7.086). Likewise, eating undercooked poultry increased the odds of disease by ~2.7 (95% CI: 1.254 – 5.103) while eating poultry prepared at establishments was found to increase the base OR by 1.801 (95% CI: 1.444 – 2.223). People who consumed *undercooked* eggs presented overall 1.248 (95% CI: 1.053 – 1.469) times the odds of becoming ill than those who consumed eggs, whereas for those who consumed *raw* eggs the mean base OR increased by a higher factor of 1.884 (95% CI: 1.283 – 2.665). Not properly washing vegetables before consumption increased the odds of salmonellosis by 1.447 (95% CI: 0.882 – 2.243) while the consumption of unpasteurised milk and cheese made of unpasteurised milk increased the odds of disease by 1.373 (95% CI: 0.878 – 2.036).

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1 Introduction

Gastro-intestinal diseases caused by a variety of bacteria, parasites and viruses represent an important public health problem around the world. In developed countries, the interest to improve the control of food-borne enteric diseases is underscored by the necessity to prevent the contamination of food and food exports; the harm to human health and its associated costs to the health sector and economy; and the harm to livestock of economic importance. In order to design effective strategies to reduce the burden of disease, an understanding of the risk factors for enteric infections is needed. However, these risk factors are wide-ranging and their identification is challenging.

An important epidemiologic approach for attributing enteric illnesses to specific risk factors is through a *case-control* design. Broadly speaking, a case-control study has been defined as an investigation into a relationship between a given disease and one or more causal or preventive factors, in which persons selected because they have the disease (i.e., cases) and suitably selected persons who do not have the disease (i.e., controls) are compared in terms on their exposure to the factor under study. Case-control studies are considered to be an alternative to cohort studies, although they are clearly distinguished by two features: (i) sampling by disease in contrast to sampling by exposure, and (ii) investigative movement from-effect-to-cause in contrast to from-cause-to-effect (Kopeck and Esdaile, 1990). In cohort studies, all potential cases are classified as exposed or unexposed. The case-control method makes the design more efficient by classifying only the actual cases.

Although case-control studies are often used during enteric disease outbreak investigations, they have been increasingly used to identify risk factors for sporadic disease. Unlike outbreak case-control studies, the purpose of a case-control study of sporadic disease is to inform public health and regulatory agencies the identified risk factors for transmission of disease at a *population* level. In an outbreak setting, the objective of a case-control study is to prevent additional illnesses by identifying the common contamination exposure. In contrast, sporadic cases of gastrointestinal disease do not share a common contamination exposure, so the odds-ratio from any single source is attenuated, making true risk differences between cases and controls more difficult to detect (Fullerton et al., 2012). For instance, even if barbecued (BBQ) chicken is an important (and known) source of campylobacteriosis, most of those servings will not be contaminated, so the odds of a patient having consumed BBQ chicken may be only slightly higher than those of a control.

The ‘diluted’ odds-ratios, characteristic of sporadic studies, can be combined by meta-analysis in order to produce a more precise estimate of the association between risk factor and disease, with an increased statistical power. Furthermore, since case-control studies are performed using different populations, different matching designs and a whole-range of other specific factors, combining them through meta-analysis would produce odds-ratio estimates that have broader generalisability than is possible using only a single study. Such well-known strengths of meta-analysis are, nonetheless, contingent on the key condition that the measures share the same theoretical concepts and are of at least satisfactory validity (related to the principle of ‘rubbish in, rubbish out’). Case-control studies are regarded as being particularly susceptible to bias, namely, selection bias, misclassification bias, recall bias and participation

bias, which can be introduced anytime in the design or conduct of the study, and can greatly impact the interpretation and validity of the study findings. Thus, case-control studies that are potential candidates for meta-analysis should first undergo a strict assessment of methodological quality.

The objective of this systematic review and meta-analysis was to synthesise, within a hierarchical categorisation of routes of transmission and host-specific factors, the associations between foodborne disease and risk factors, by meta-analysing odds-ratio measures extracted from *relevant* case-control or cohort studies. The enteric diseases, for which such primary studies were gathered, were those caused by *Salmonella* spp, *Campylobacter*, Shiga-toxin *Escherichia coli* (STEC), *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Toxoplasma gondii*, Norovirus, Hepatitis A virus, Hepatitis E virus, *Cryptosporidium* spp. and *Giardia duodenalis*. Since primary studies investigate a variety of potential determinants of disease, a risk categorisation scheme was developed for this meta-analysis study, which included travel, host-specific factors and pathways of exposure – comprising person-to-person, animal, environment and food routes of transmission. In this way, the risk factors as labelled in the primary studies underwent a harmonisation that supported the integration and combination of results from all collected studies.

2 Methodology

As in any systematic review and meta-analysis, a methodical and reproducible procedure was employed (Figure 1). Briefly, for each foodborne hazard, meta-analysis began with a delineation of the review question; clear enough to lead to the definition of keywords for literature search. After screening each reference record for relevance and methodological quality, previously-defined qualitative and quantitative information was extracted from the case-control/cohort studies. The joint meta-analytical data was first described using basic statistics. Next, partitioning of data by meaningful categories was appraised in order to make the most of the information contained in the (normally-sparse) meta-analytical data sets. Meta-analyses were fitted to the data partitions or subsets. Influential diagnostics statistics were checked for every meta-analysis model in order to remove any influential odds-ratio originating from studies deemed as having some potential for bias. Publication bias was also evaluated. The steps are explained in details, as follows.

2.1 Definition of the review question

Following the EFSA's guidelines for systematic reviews on food and feed safety assessments (EFSA, 2010), the review question was identified to have a typical PECO structure (viz. *population*, *exposure*, *comparator* and *outcome* as key elements) since it seeks to evaluate the relationship between a (risk) factor and a population exposed to it. However, it must be born in mind that the fact that individual studies specify different risk factors makes the review question to be of a rather *open* nature. An open-framed question is a question that lacks some specification; in our case, the risk factors. While most of the question's key elements can be identified, the *exposure* is study-specific.

Figure 1. Schematic of the steps followed for the meta-analysis of case-control/cohort studies of enteric diseases

The question's key elements were broken down, as follows:

Population: Cases of foodborne diseases in humans, which can be children, adults, elderly, immunocompromised or mixed population.

Comparator: A control made up of individuals free of disease, or with another disease

Outcome: Odds ratio (OR) and, when given, population attributable fraction (PAF)

Exposure: Risk factors of the specific foodborne disease

The exposure is given by the possible determinants of foodborne human disease, which is precisely what the review question of this meta-analysis study seeks to assess. Each primary study determined a specific set of risk factors or routes of transmission, which were attributed to defined categories at a later stage.

2.2 Literature search

Literature search for the 14 biological hazards was conducted in October and November 2016, and was limited to the languages English, French, Portuguese and Spanish. However, no restrictions were defined for the year of the study. Relevant studies were identified from the bibliographic search engine Science Direct, PubMed, Scielo, ISI Web of Science and Scopus, using a combination of keywords of *general terms*, *foodborne hazard* and *additional terms*, joined by the logical connector AND.

General terms (Title/Abstract/Keywords):

“case-control” OR “risk factor”

Foodborne hazard (Title/Abstract/Keywords):

(*Salmonella* OR salmonellosis) OR (Campylobacter OR campylobacteriosis) OR (Shigatoxin Escherichia coli OR Shigatoxin E coli OR STEC OR VTEC OR EHEC OR 0157:H7 OR O26:H11 OR O145:H28 OR O103:H2 OR O111:H8 OR O104:H4) OR (Listeria monocytogenes OR listeriosis) OR (Yersinia enterocolitica OR yersiniosis) OR Bacillus cereus OR Clostridium perfringens OR Staphylococcus aureus OR (Toxoplasma gondii OR toxoplasmosis) OR Norovirus OR Hepatitis A OR Hepatitis E OR (Cryptosporidium OR cryptosporidiosis) OR (Giardia duodenalis OR giardiasis)

Additional terms (Title/Abstract/Keywords):

infection OR disease OR intoxication

The term “sporadic” was not added because case-control or cohort studies conducted during outbreak investigations were also integrated into the reference databases. For each biological hazard, the records from the five search engines were combined into a single reference database in Zotero. Using this software, duplicate references were carefully checked and deleted. Table 1 lists the number of citations recovered by bibliographic search engine and the total number of references after duplicate removal for each of the foodborne hazards under study. For most of the hazards, the search engines Web of Science and Scopus retrieved together more citations than Science Direct, PubMed and Scielo combined. Nonetheless, searches were still conducted in Science Direct, PubMed and Scielo because their results were by no means contained in those from the broader engines. The Scielo engine, for instance,

retrieved articles mostly in Portuguese and Spanish carried out in Latin America. The large volumes of bibliographic citations were managed in both Zotero and JabRef.

Table 1. Number of records retrieved by search engine along with the total number of records without duplicates per bibliographic database (foodborne hazard)

	Science Direct	Pub-Med	SciELO	Web of Science	Scopus	Total w/o duplicates
<i>Salmonella</i>	636	756	46	2456	5457	3858
<i>Campylobacter</i>	308	727	12	1141	2265	2360
<i>E. coli</i>	978	951	460	2693	1113	4718
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	1307	255	78	489	2399	1902
<i>Y. enterocolitica</i>	36	62	25	110	574	477
<i>B. cereus</i>	45	15	55	218	589	513
<i>C. perfringens</i>	64	50	34	264	517	641
<i>S. aureus</i>	1009	1304	351	3794	747	5136
<i>Toxoplasma</i>	345	329	15	866	1210	1640
Norovirus	98	96	21	365	457	672
Hepatitis A	176	268	127	153	1316	1624
Hepatitis E	61	100	127	58	429	614
<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	211	207	51	1082	3539	1985
<i>Giardia</i>	61	69	29	352	788	691

2.3 Screening for relevance

A bibliographic database was built per pathogen. Each of the titles and abstracts from the 14 bibliographic databases was subjected to screening for its relevance to answering the review question. Relevance was assessed on the basis of (i) human disease; and (ii) case-control study conducted as part of *sporadic illness* or *outbreak* investigation. However, except for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, cohort studies reporting either relative risk (RR) or odds ratio (OR) were also included in the meta-analysis. Full-texts of the relevant records were then obtained and read throughout by two researchers in order to assess their suitability for inclusion in the meta-analysis. The criteria for inclusion were as follows:

- (i) disease in humans caused by any of the aforementioned hazards;
- (ii) case-control (or cohort) study design;
- (iii) information on case definition; and
- (iv) quality and completeness of statistical analysis, including OR/RRs or, at least, sufficient information to calculate OR.

2.4 Assessment of methodological quality

The methodological quality of each primary study included underwent a standardised assessment utilising a checklist comprised of six areas of concern:

- a. Appropriate selection of the control, in order to avoid *selection bias*;
- b. Adjustment to - at least partially - correct for confounders. The relevant confusion factors were collected;

- c. Strategy for the comparability: acceptable matching criteria for matched study designs (viz. age and gender)
- d. Proper data analysis depending on type of design, matched or unmatched;
- e. Acceptable responses rates for exposed and control
- f. Provision of crude and/or adjusted odds ratio (OR) and either confidence interval or p-value.
- g. Overall quality of underlying methods, appropriate statistics, sensible data and quality of reporting (combination of criteria a-f)

Each of the items was answered by yes/no. Studies that failed to meet at least one of the checklist items – except item (g) – were identified as “having potential for bias”. Studies that failed to meet item (g) were discarded from the SR.

2.5 Data extraction

From the primary studies, the following information was extracted whenever available:

- a) **Country:** The country where the study was undertaken.
- b) **Year:** It refers to the starting year of the study.
- c) **Year Category:** It is comprised of two strata: “Before 2000” and “After 2000”, depending on the year the case-control study started.
- d) **Region:** Refers to the geographical region where the case study was conducted. They were: North America, South America, Northern Europe, Southern Europe, Western Europe, Easter Europe, Oceania and Asia.
- e) **Serotype:** Categorical variable indicating serotype. When the case-control study focused on *Salmonella* spp., results were entered into the serotype class “Undefined”. For studies that recovered many serotypes from case patients, the serotype class “Various” was used. When a case-control study encompassed both serotypes Typhimurium and Enteritidis, results were assigned to the serotype category “Typhimurium/Enteritidis”.
- f) **Phage type:** This information was annotated for case-control studies that investigated risk factors associated to specific phage types, so it was not available for all studies.
- g) **Study type:** A categorical variable that takes one of two classes: “Sporadic” or “Outbreak”. For *Salmonella* spp., and *Campylobacter*, data were extracted only from case-control studies of sporadic illness.
- h) **Population:** This categorical variable indicates the type of population targeted by the case-control/cohort study. The classes were defined as: “Children”, “Adult”, “Susceptible” (for the immunocompromised and elderly population) and “Mixed” (when the target population was any combination of the classes above).
- i) **Case definition:** This categorical variable refers to whether confirmed or probable cases were used in the case-control study, and is comprised of three classes: “Symptom-based” if the diagnosis of all of the cases of the study is made on the grounds of symptoms only; these are characteristic clinical features of the disease; “Lab-based” if the pathogen was isolated from a stool or blood culture for all of the cases; and “Either” if the diagnosis of some cases was symptom-based while the others had lab-confirmation.
- j) **Number of cases:** A numeric variable indicating the number of cases included in the case-control investigation; or the number of ill people in a cohort study.

- k) **Number of exposed cases:** Numeric variable indicating the number of cases that were exposed to the risk factor for which the OR/RR was calculated.
- l) **Median age of cases:** When stated, the median age of the cases was annotated.
- m) **Number of controls:** A numeric variable indicating the number of controls included in the case-control study; or the number of non-ill people in a cohort study.
- n) **Number of exposed controls:** Numeric variable indicating the number of controls that were exposed to the risk factor for which the OR/RR was calculated.
- o) **Median age of controls:** Not always given, but when stated, the median age of the controls was extracted.
- p) **Design:** It is a two-class categorical variable that refers to the type of sampling of controls used in the study. The design of a case-control study was defined as “unmatched” when the control group was selected at random, or more often, when the case individuals were selected in such a way that their distribution of certain intrinsic variable(s), for instance, age, was similar to that of the case group (also known, as frequency-matching). The design variable was set to “Matched” when controls were selected by case to match individual cases in certain specified respects (i.e., matching variables or confounders) so that one or more controls are paired to every case. An important use of matching is to control for complex confounders that cannot be quantified for use in a later regression adjustment analysis (for instance, residence, in an attempt to control for a range of environmental and sociological factors).
- q) **Model:** This categorical variable indicates the type of model employed to calculate OR and its confidence interval/p-value; and takes one of four classes: “Chi”, “MH”, “UL” or “CL”. When OR was computed in a crude way and the association between illness and risk factor was tested using a chi-square test or a Pearson’s chi-square test, the class assigned to the variable Model was “Chi”. The second class was labelled as “MH”, which stands for the Mantel and Haenszel method for testing association, commonly applied in frequency-matched and matched data. Unlike the chi-square method, MH is a method that controls confounding, although it cannot accommodate continuous confounders. The third class “UL” stands for unconditional logistic regression, and refers to ORs calculated by a logistic regression (mostly) for unmatched case-control studies, while the fourth class “CL” is chosen when ORs are determined by means of a conditional logistic regression in a matched case-control setting.
- r) **Analysis type:** This is another categorical variable that denotes whether OR was computed in a univariate analysis (also called bivariate analysis; “Uni”) or in a multivariate analysis (“Multi”). The variable Analysis Type was inevitably linked to the variable Model, since the models to compute ORs in a univariate way could be any of them: “Chi”, “MH”, “UL” or “CL”. By contrary, ORs from a multivariate analysis can only be adjusted by “UL” or “CL” (Table 2).
- s) **OR type:** Another way to characterise the type of model used to compute the OR was through the broadly-used denomination “Raw” or “Adjusted”. “Raw” was assigned to ORs that were calculated with no adjustment for confounders. Obviously, ORs tested by the chi-square model were always of the raw type. ORs produced by MH could be either “Raw” if calculated as a ratio of discordant pairs, or “Adjusted”, if modified by the effect of strata (i.e., weighted average of ORs from the different strata of a confounder). In univariate analysis, it was assumed that both the “UL” and “CL” could produce “Raw” ORs if there were no other explanatory variables apart from *one* tested exposure in the logistic regressions. By contrary, an OR obtained through the “UL” or “CL” model was deemed as “Adjusted” if at least one demographic variable

or confounder was fitted along with the one tested exposure as explanatory variables of the logistic regression. When the data analysis conducted was multivariate, the ORs obtained were always considered to be “Adjusted”, since by definition the associations of illness with many exposures and, sometimes cofounders or demographic features, were all determined from a single regression.

- t) **Risk factor:** The risk factors or possible determinants of foodborne disease, outlined in the primary studies and for which ORs were available, were assigned to three main categories: predisposing factors specific to the host by the time of disease (“HostSpecific”), those related to different pathways of exposure (“Pathway”) and travel (“Travel”).

Table 2. Interrelationships between type of analysis, models and OR type considered for the meta-analytical data

Analysis type	Model	OR type
Univariate analysis	Chi-square	Raw
	Mantel-Haenzel	Raw or adjusted
	Unconditional logistic	Raw or adjusted
	Conditional logistic	Raw or adjusted
Multivariate analysis	Unconditional logistic	Adjusted
	Conditional logistic	Adjusted

- u) **Subcategory, route and food class:** These are categorical variables that store the hierarchy within each risk factor in order to facilitate subsequent data partitions and analyses (Table 3). For the “Travel” risk factor, three subcategories were considered: (i) travel within the country where the case-control study was performed (“Inside”); (ii) travel abroad (“Abroad”); and (iii) any kind of travel/not stated (“Any”). For the group of “HostSpecific” risk factors, the subcategories were: (i) use of anti-acids, such as proton-pump-inhibitors, before the onset of the disease (“Antiacids”); (ii) use of antimicrobials or antibiotics before the onset of the disease (“Antibiotics”); (iii) being a breastfed infant (“Breastfeeding”); (iv) suffering from any chronic (-like) disease, such as diabetes mellitus or cancer (“Chronic”); and (v) use of medications other than anti-acids/antibiotics or suffering from any other medical condition, such as the recent use of thyroid drugs or any gastro-intestinal condition (“OtherMed”). For “Pathway”, which is the largest risk factor group, four categories were created: (i) person-to-person transmission (“Person2Person”); (ii) transmission from petting, visiting and handling animals (“Animals”); (iii) transmission from contaminated water and environments (“Environment”); and (iv) transmission from the consumption of contaminated food (“Food”). The subcategory of animal-related transmission of disease was further subdivided into four routes: (i) contact with farm animals (“FarmA”); (ii) contact with pets (“Pet”); (iii) contact with wild animals (“Wild”); and (iv) occupational exposure from working with food-producing animals, in an abattoir/butcher’s or being a veterinary (“Occupational”). The subcategory of environmental sources of transmission is comprised of six mutually-exclusive routes: (i) attendance to day care institution, such as crèches or elderly home (“DayCare”); (ii)

sources of drinking water, such as water well, surface water or municipal water (“DrinkWater”); (iii) exposures to recreational water, such as swimming in a lake/river, sailing, fishing or canoeing (“RecWater”); (iv) exposure to farm or rural environment, such as living on or visiting a farm (“FarmE”); and (v) exposure to contaminated objects and environments, such as children touching soil in parks or playing in a sandbox (“Playground”); and (vi) exposure related to waste water, sewage and poor sanitation conditions (“WasteWater”). The subcategory “Food” was subdivided into the nine routes “Meat”, “Eggs”, “Dairy”, “Produce”, “Grains”, “Seafood”, “Beverages”, “Composite”, and “Sugars”. As shown in Table 3, the variable “FoodClass” pertained only to food-related exposures, and enabled a further break down of the routes. The route “Meat” consists of six food classes: “Beef” for any way of consuming beef meat; “Pork” for any way of consuming pork meat; “Poultry” for consuming any poultry meat; “OtherRedMeat” for other red meats such as lamb or venison meat; “ProcMeat” for any type of processed meat such as ham, sausages, bacon, burger, cold meats, etc; and “Others” for unclassifiable meats (for instance, risk labels such as *any red meat*, *BBQ meat*, *any meat*, etc.). The route “Eggs” is divided into “Eggs” for any way to prepare and consume eggs (i.e., runny eggs, scrambled eggs, hard-boiled eggs, etc.) and “EggProd” for egg products, and raw-egg-containing dishes and desserts. The route “Dairy” encompasses six food classes: “Milk” for any type of raw or unpasteurised milk, “Cheese” for any type of fresh, semi-matured or matured cheese, “Fermented” for any fermented milk or yogurt, “Fats” for dairy-origin high-fat foods such as butter, cream and ice-cream, “Powder” for any powder milk or infant formula, and “UndefinedD” for any undistinguishable dairy source (for instance, *dairy products*, *dairy other than cheese*, etc.). The route “Produce” breaks down into nine food classes: “Fruits” for any kind of fruit; “Vegetables” for vegetables except roots, legumes, nuts and sprouts (for instance, leafy greens, onion, pepper, cabbage, tomatoes, cucumber, etc.); “Roots” for root vegetables such as radishes, potatoes, carrots and cassava; “Legumes” for grain legumes such as peas, lentils and beans; “Sprouts” for alfalfa and bean sprouts; “Fungi” for any type of edible fungi, “Nuts” for almonds, chestnut, pecans, walnuts, etc.; “Spices” for herbs and spices such as chicory, basil, coriander, black pepper, oregano, curry, parsley, etc; and “VegProd” for vegetable products such as pickles, liquid spices, etc. The route “Grains” consists of four classes: “Baked” for any baked goods such as bread, cake, pastry, etc.; “Cereals” for any way of consuming cereals grains such as boiled rice, kous-kous or cereal breakfast; “Pasta” for boiled pasta; and “OthersG” for an unclassifiable type of grain-derived food. The route “Seafood” further breaks down into five food classes: “Fish” for any kind of fish; “Crustaceans” for any type of crustacean; “Molluscs” for any kind of mollusc; “Processed” for any processed seafood such as canned tuna chunks or smoked salmon; and “UndefinedS” used when the type of seafood was not properly specified in the case-control study (for instance, *eating seafood*). The route of beverages is composed of “Bottled water”, “Alcoholic” for any alcoholic drink, “SoftDrink” for soda and soft drinks, “Juices” for fruit juices, concentrates and smoothies, and “UndefinedB” when the beverage type is not indicated. While the route “Sugars” encompassed foodstuff such as chocolate and confectionary, and was not broken down any further, the route “Composite” consisted of the five food classes: “RTE composite” for any ready-to-eat multi-ingredient meal including RTE sandwiches; “Sandwich” for sandwiches prepared at home or bought at an establishment; “Dishes” for dishes and soups prepared at home or consumed in restaurants; “Fast-food” for any sort of fast-food meal such as chicken wings or

hamburger as long as they were bought at a fast-food establishment; and “OthersC” for multi-ingredient meals for which no information was given.

Table 3. Hierarchy of risk factors defined for transmission of enteric diseases, as stored in the variables “Subcategory”, “Route” and “Food Class” in meta-analytical data sets

Risk Factor	Subcategory	Route	Food Class	
Travel	Any			
	Abroad			
	Inside			
Host-specific	Anti-acids			
	Antimicrobials			
	Breastfed			
	Chronic diseases			
	Other med conditions			
Pathway	Person to person			
	Animals	Farm animals		
		Pets		
		Wild animals		
		Occupational exp.		
	Environment	Day care		
		Drink water		
		Recreational water		
		Farm/rural environ.		
		Playground		
		Waste water		
	Food	Meat		Beef
				Pork
				Other red meats
				Poultry
			Processed meat	
		Others		
Egg			Eggs	
			Egg products	
Dairy			Milk	
			Cheese	
		Fermented		
		Fats		
		Powder		
Produce		Undefined		
		Fruits		
		Vegetables		
		Roots		
		Legumes		
		Sprouts		
		Fungi		
		Nuts		
		Spices & Herbs		
	Veg products			

Grains	Baked goods Cereals Pasta Others
Seafood	Fish Crustaceans Molluscs Processed Undefined
Beverages	Bottled water Alcoholic Soft drink Juices Undefined
Composite	RTE composite Sandwich Dishes – restaurant (including soups) Dishes – fast-food Others
Sugars	No further class

- v) **RTE:** The RTE variable acts as a flag that takes the value of “1” when the foodstuff is said or known to be ready-to-eat (for instance, cheese, ham, RTE meal, etc.).
- w) **Setting:** On some occasions, the location of the exposure to foods was specified in the primary study. For **sporadic** case-control studies, the risk factors associated to food consumption were further classified into “Home” when the food was prepared in the household, and “EatingOut” when the food was consumed at a restaurant, café, bakery, fast-food establishment, buffet, party, banquette or at any social gathering. In cases, where data were extracted from studies investigating **outbreaks**, a third class of setting was included, which is “Institution”. An institutional setting where an outbreak occurs is defined as a hospital, nursing or assisted-living home, long-term care facility, school, university, prison, detention centre and the like.
- x) **Handling:** This is categorical variable that provides additional information on how the food is prepared, handled and consumed. The classes are: “Raw” to indicate that the exposure concerns raw food (for instance: *unpasteurised milk, cake dough with raw eggs, raw fish*); “Undercooked” to signal that the food was not fully cooked (for example: *undercooked chicken, runny eggs*); “Unwashed” for foods that were not washed or thoroughly washing prior to consumption/preparation (for instance, *unwashed leafy green, unwashed carrots*); “Poor” for any practice revealing poor hygiene during food preparation (example: *rarely washing hands while cooking, no washing chopping boards between raw meat and cooked food, dirt in fridge, etc.*); and “Preparation” to indicate that the exposure detailed in the primary study refers to food preparation practices and habits (for example: *thaws meat in water, reheats in microwave, use of glass chopping board as opposed to wooden chopping board*).
- y) **Label:** Label is not a variable for analysis, but a record of the exact description of the vehicle of transmission hypothesised to be associated with illness, as appears in the primary study. It is the label that leads to the complete stratification of the risk factor into subcategory, route, food class, setting, handling and RTE status. Some examples

of labels are: *Any reptile or amphibian as pet, animal contact without handwashing, chicken curry from take away*. Labels are not only useful for keeping a record of the original description of the exposure, but also for the construction of forest plots.

- z) **Odds ratio:** A quantitative variable measuring the association between potential exposure and enteric illness as odds ratio. This measure could be either directly extracted from the primary study or calculated from the information given. When data were extracted from cohort studies, OR was computed from RR, using the equation:

$$OR = \frac{RR(1-p_0)}{1-p_0RR} \quad (1)$$

where p_0 is the proportion of positive outcomes in the unexposed group.

- aa) **OR lower and upper:** The 95% confidence interval (CI) was also extracted, in order to calculate the standard error of the OR. When the p-value of the association measure was stated while the CI was omitted from the report, the standard error (SE) of the OR was computed as,

$$SE = \frac{OR}{|z|} \quad (2)$$

with z corresponding to the given p-value.

- bb) **p-value:** The probability value corresponding to the OR estimate was annotated whenever available.
- cc) **Matching criteria:** This is a list of variables that, in the primary study's *design*, were described as the matching variables or confounders to match at least one control to a case patient. The matching criteria field was only filled out for matched case-control studies.
- dd) **Adjusting criteria:** This is a list of variables that, in the primary study's *statistical analysis*, were described as the confounders or demographic/socioeconomic variables utilised to adjust the OR estimates. These confounders are the explanatory variables, apart from the exposures, inserted into a univariate or multivariate logistic regression. When the "MH" model was employed the treat the data, and produced an OR of the "Adjusted" type, the adjusting criterion corresponds to the stratifying factor (for example, age strata, gender, etc.).
- ee) **Potential for bias:** A case-control study is well known to be susceptible to selection bias, although other types of bias such as misclassification, recall and participation bias can undermine the validity of the study findings (i.e., ultimate OR values to meta-analyse). Thus, each of the primary studies was subjected to a stringent assessment of the methodological quality, with the aid of a purposely-designed *quality check form* (Figure 2). This quality check form acted as a reminder of the methodological elements to be taken into account in a stepwise manner to reach up the final decision on the study's potential for flawed results. For each of the ORs extracted, the variable "BiasPotential" could take one of two possible values: "0" to denote that the case-control study was judged to be of at least acceptable methodological quality, and "1" to denote possible methodological flaws that could result in bias estimates. According to the step-by-step quality check form (Figure 2), the OR estimates from a case-control study could be potentially biased if cases are not properly defined, if controls are not healthy people but have another gastrointestinal illness (viz. a case-case analysis may underestimate the strength of the OR association if exposures are shared), if the statistical analysis was not appropriate for the study design, or even if

sufficient information was not given for the researcher's appraisal of the methodological quality.

Study ID	
Study design	
	Case definition
	Are healthy controls used?
	Type of design
	Unmatched <input type="checkbox"/>
	Random sampling <input type="checkbox"/>
	Frequency matching <input type="checkbox"/>
	Matched <input type="checkbox"/>
	Individual matching <input type="checkbox"/>
	Matching criteria/Confounders:
	Target population
	Case response rates acceptable?
	Control response rates acceptable?
	Are power and sample size calculations reported?
Exposure assessment	
	Was standard questionnaire used?
	Method of interview (phone, face-to-face, self-administered)
Analysis	
	Method of analysis
	Chi-square <input type="checkbox"/> MH <input type="checkbox"/> Logistic <input type="checkbox"/> Conditional logistic <input type="checkbox"/>
	Is the method appropriate for the design?
	Are univariate Odd Ratios reported?
	Are they adjusted for confounders? Which?
	Are multivariate Odd Ratios reported?
	Are they adjusted for confounders? Which?
	Are PAF values reported?
Potential for bias	
	Quality of reporting
Overall	<input type="checkbox"/> Not sufficient information to judge = 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Strong evidence of bias = 1 Controls had another GI condition, inappropriate design/data analysis <input type="checkbox"/> Standard rules of case-control studies = 0 <input type="checkbox"/> Above standard rules of case-control studies = 0

Figure 2. Methodological quality assessment form that informed the decision on the study's potential for having arrived to a biased OR estimate

cc) **Population attributable fraction.** Values of PAF and their 95% confidence intervals were excerpted from the published studies whenever available.

2.6 Relevant issues on strategies for inclusion of ORs

- a) When primary studies investigated associations between risk factors and disease in both univariate and multivariate mode, both estimates were extracted, as they are duly identified as “Uni” or “Multi” by the variable “Analysis Type”.
- b) Risk factors presenting a significant protective effect, with no clear reason or justification, were not extracted. For example, protective effect of the consumption of vegetables against salmonellosis.

2.7 Synthesis of research of the risk factors for enteric disease transmission

The meta-analytical synthesis of the associations between transmission of enteric disease and risk factors/host-specific factors was performed separately for every biological hazard. In general, the analyses sought to meet five objectives:

- a) Descriptive statistics of the meta-analytical data on risk factors of disease;
- b) Calculation of the overall risks of disease for travel, host-specific factors and transmission pathways related to animal contact and contaminated environment and food;
- c) Calculation of the overall risks of disease from consumption of ready-to-eat and barbecued foods;
- d) Calculation of the overall effects of food handling and food preparation setting on risk of disease; and
- e) Graphical synthesis of the risks associated to poor handling and preparation of foods.

However, the five data analysis objectives delineated above could not be fulfilled for all of the biological hazards, due to either insufficient data or data sparseness. The meta-analysis procedures for each of the five research synthesis objectives are detailed, as follows.

2.7.1 *Descriptive statistics*

Bar plots or pie diagrams of the number of ORs extracted by population, serovar, country, experimental design, risk factor, analysis type, model type, OR type, and publication bias status were built to provide an overview of the meta-analytical data sets.

2.7.2 *Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal- and food-related pathways of transmission*

To calculate the overall risk of disease per risk factor, subcategory, route and food class, data was partitioned by: travel, host-specific factors, person-to-person, environment-, animal- and food-related routes of transmission. First, a simple meta-analysis model was adjusted to a data

partition to evaluate the effect of the geographical region (r) on the association between exposure and illness (i.e., odds-ratio OR),

$$\begin{aligned} \log OR_{ir} &= \beta_{0i} + \beta_{1r} \text{Region}_r + \varepsilon_{ir} \\ \beta_{0i} &= \bar{\beta}_0 + u_i \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

To extract the evident variability due to the different primary studies i , the model's intercept β_{0i} was allowed to shift according to the random effect u_i due to the deviation of the primary study i from the true estimate. The random effects u_i were assumed to be normally-distributed with mean zero and variance s^2_u . Notice that the between-study variance s^2_u is the variance widely known as τ^2 in meta-analysis. The errors or residuals ε_{ir} were also assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean zero and variance s^2 .

Next, the general meta-analysis model was fitted,

$$\begin{aligned} \log OR_{ijk t} &= \beta_{0i} + \beta_{1tj} \text{AnalysisType}_t + \beta_{2k} \text{Subgroup}_k + \varepsilon_{ijk t} \\ \beta_{1tj} &= \bar{\beta}_{1t} + v_{tj} \\ \beta_{0i} &= \bar{\beta}_0 + u_i \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where k is a subgroup class that depends on data partition. For instance, if the data partition is Travel, the subgroup variable contains the classes: Inside, Abroad and Any. Similarly, if the data partition is Eggs, the subgroup is comprised of the classes Eggs and Egg Products. The primary study is denoted by i , while each of the two types of analysis, multivariate or univariate, is denoted by t . For multivariate analysis ($t=1$), model type j takes two levels (unconditional logistic and conditional logistic) whereas for univariate analysis ($t=2$), model type j takes four levels (chi-square, Mantel-Haenszel, unconditional logistic and conditional logistic) (Table 2). It is expected that the type of model used to compute log OR, either in univariate or multivariate analysis, confers variability to the values. To extract this variability from the overall estimates, slope random effects v_{tj} with model j as subject of variation were placed on "AnalysisType". This strategy produced random effects v_{1j} for log OR obtained from multivariate analysis and v_{2j} for log OR obtained from univariate analysis. These slope random effects were assumed to follow normal distributions with mean zero and variances s^2_{v1} and s^2_{v2} , respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} v_{1j} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s^2_{v1}) \\ v_{2j} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s^2_{v2}) \end{aligned}$$

As before, the random effects u_i due to primary studies were assumed to be normally-distributed with mean zero and variance s^2_u . The errors or residuals ε_{ijk} were also assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean zero and variance s^2 .

$$\begin{aligned} u_i &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s^2_u) \\ \varepsilon_{ijk t} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s^2) \end{aligned}$$

In Equation (4), the effect of year category (i.e., before 2000 and after 2000) was also evaluated. The year category covariate was dropped from the model if its associated value was higher than 0.15. Else, it remained in the model and the overall ORs of each subgroup were estimated with basis on the recent primary studies (year category after 2000).

2.7.3 *Meta-analysis on the risk of gastrointestinal illness transmission by consumption of ready-to-eat foods and barbecued foods*

For some microbiological hazards, two additional meta-analysis models were adjusted in order to estimate the overall risk of transmission of illness through the consumption of RTE foods and BBQ foods. Two data partitions were created, one that gathered all data for which the “RTE” variable status was “1”, and another that brought together all data whose labels contained the word “BBQ”. Due to the fewer data points contained in these partitions, meta-analytical models were simplified, according to Equation (5),

$$\begin{aligned}\log OR_i &= \beta_{0i} + \varepsilon_i \\ \beta_{0i} &= \bar{\beta}_0 + u_i \\ u_i &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s_u^2) \\ \varepsilon_i &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s^2)\end{aligned}\tag{5}$$

where $\bar{\beta}_0$ is the overall OR. Model (4) was adjusted separately to the RTE and BBQ data partitions.

2.7.4 *Meta-analysis on the effects of handling and setting on the risk of enteric illness transmission by food consumption*

The second group of meta-analyses only pertained to food classes. In order to obtain overall estimates of the effects of handling (m = raw, undercooked, unwashed) and setting (n = home, eating out) on the risk of contracting an enteric illness, the general meta-analysis model:

$$\begin{aligned}\log OR_{ijtmn} &= \beta_{0i} + \beta_{1tj} \text{AnalysisType}_t + \beta_{2m} \text{Handling}_m + \beta_{3n} \text{Setting}_n + \varepsilon_{ijtmn} \\ \beta_{1tj} &= \bar{\beta}_{1t} + v_{tj} \\ \beta_{0i} &= \bar{\beta}_0 + u_i \\ v_{1j} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s_{v1}^2) \\ v_{2j} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s_{v2}^2) \\ u_i &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s_u^2) \\ \varepsilon_{ijtmn} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, s^2)\end{aligned}\tag{6}$$

was fitted to the food-class data partitions where sufficient data was available to obtain reliable estimates. This model differs from that of Equation (4) in that the fixed effect of subgroup was removed, as for the data partitions used in this third group of meta-analysis there is no further breakdown of food classes. The effects of AnalysisType β_{1tj} as well as their random effects error structure remain in the model so as to extract the variability in log OR due to the type of analysis t and the model type j . Similarly, the between-study variance s^2_u remained in the general model.

When for some data partitions the variances s^2_{v1} and s^2_{v2} of the random effects v_{1j} and v_{2j} , respectively, were non-significant in the full models (3) or (5), the random effects were removed and the general model was simplified to consider only a fixed-effects for AnalysisType. When data points were too few in at least one of the classes of analysis type (for instance, very few multivariate odds ratios in contrast to the univariate odds ratios), the model was further abridged by removing AnalysisType fixed-effects. However, the allowance for the random effects u_i accounting for the between-study variability s^2_u was maintained in all meta-analytical partitions. All meta-analysis models (3), (4), (5) and (6) were essentially weighted mixed-effects linear regression models with weights defined as the inverse of the sampling variance of the reported ORs.

The outputs of the final meta-analysis models adjusted to the different data partitions are presented in a tabulated format including fixed-effects estimates (in log OR scale) and variances of the random-effects and residuals. In addition, the results from the test of residual heterogeneity (QE) and the omnibus test of moderators (QM) are shown. A significant QE statistic indicates the presence of residual between-study heterogeneity that could not be fully explained by the moderators already considered in the meta-analysis model. A significant QM statistic denotes that at least one of the classes of the moderating variable considered (Subgroup) differs statistically from the others (Viechtbauer, 2010). The QM test was conducted on the Subgroup variable of Equation (4) in order to evaluate differences between its classes. For instance, in the meta-analysis fitted to the eggs data partition, the QM test would allow assessing whether the pooled log ORs of the classes Eggs and Egg Products are significantly different.

2.7.5 Risk of gastrointestinal illness transmission due to poor handling and preparation of foods

Some case-control studies assessed the influence of a series of exposures related to poor handling and forms of preparation of food. While the ORs linked to those exposures were also excerpted from the case-control studies, there was not an evident way to group them in meaningful categories. Hence, it was considered that the best way to bring them together was by means of a forest plot graphical display. Forest plots of the composite type were built to separate exposures according to type of population

2.8 Influential diagnosis of the risk measures with potential for bias

For each of the meta-analysis conducted on a data partition, the Cook's distance approach was used to assess the influence of a data point on the meta-analysis estimates. When an

influential point was present (observation whose Cook's distance was higher than 1.0), its validity was examined by checking its "potential for bias" status ("0" or "1"). If that particular OR measure was flagged as "1" (i.e., potentially biased), the observation was removed, and the meta-analysis model was re-adjusted. Figure 3 shows an example of the procedure described above for the meta-analysis conducted on the risk factors of salmonellosis related to travel. Notice that, in this real case, the observation #47 was potentially-biased ("1" next to the marker), and therefore it was removed from the Travel data partition of *Salmonella* spp.

Figure 3. An example of the use of Cook's distance as decision criterion for removal of potentially-biased odds ratios from the data sets

2.9 Assessment of publication bias

In meta-analysis, it is widely known that if studies with small or non-significant results remain unpublished, the plot of the effect sizes and their standard errors produce an asymmetric funnel plot. One may be able to detect such asymmetry by testing whether the observed outcomes (or residuals from a model with moderators) are related to their corresponding sampling variances, standard errors, or more simply, sample sizes (Viechtbauer, 2010). Thus, for the meta-analysis of every data partition, publication bias was first graphically assessed by the funnel plot of the residuals from the fitted model and their corresponding inverse standard errors. Next, the presence of publication bias was formally tested by including total sample size (total sample size was defined as the sum of the number of cases and controls) as a covariate in the meta-analysis regression models. So, in a separate regression, the total sample size was added to Equations 4-6 as an additional covariate. If the p-value associated to total sample size was non-significant (i.e., no effect of study size on the measured ORs), we concluded that the existence of a file-drawer problem was unlikely (Hox and de Leeuw, 2003) for the reported ORs of the data partition.

3 Results

3.1 *Salmonella* spp.

3.1.1 *Descriptive statistics*

In the systematic review of risk factors pertaining to the human infection with salmonellosis, a total of 3858 bibliographic sources were identified, from which 318 passed the screening for relevance comprising case-control studies from both sporadic illnesses and outbreaks. However, for *Salmonella*, meta-analysis was undertaken only on sporadic disease. The quality assessment stage was passed by 69 primary studies investigating sporadic salmonellosis, which were conducted between 1987 and 2013. These primary studies provided a total of 1304 categorised odds-ratios for meta-analysis, which investigated risks of transmission of different *Salmonella* serovars. While the majority of ORs were available for illness caused by (*Salmonella enterica* subsp. *Enterica*) serovars Enteritidis, Typhimurium, undefined spp. and a combination of Enteritidis/Typhimurium, fewer ORs were reported for the risks of transmission of Birkenhead, Brandenburg, Heidelberg, Infantis, Javiana, Mikawasima, Mississippi, Napoli, Newport, Tennessee and Virchow (Figure 3). The countries with the highest number of case-control studies for sporadic salmonellosis were USA (21), UK (10), Germany (6) and Canada (4), which produced all together 65% of the meta-analytical data. Out of 69 studies, eighteen studies investigated exposures in children and infants, and eight in the adult population, while only one study focused on the immunocompromised population. Because exposures were investigated in the mixed population much more frequently (996 ORs) than in the adult population (87 ORs) (Figure 4), the ORs coming from the adult population were moved to the category “Mixed” for later meta-analysis. However, as a rule, because of their distinct routes of exposure, the children and mixed populations were not assessed in a single meta-analysis model, but in separate meta-analyses. Data from both age groups were combined only when the ORs belonging to the children population were too few to run a separate meta-analysis model.

Forty-eight case-control studies (65%) employed a matched design and produced a total of 804 categorised ORs. While 124 ORs were computed in multivariate analysis, 680 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated using MH (321) and CL (301); some of them by UL (124) and the simple chi-square test (58). From the case-control studies that used an unmatched or frequency-matched design (26 studies), 339 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while 160 in multivariate analysis. Most of the ORs from unmatched designs were estimated using UL (251) and chi-square (194), whereas 54 ORs were MH-estimates adjusted by a confounder’s strata. Bringing together the matched and unmatched designs, 750 extracted ORs were not adjusted by any confounder, while 554 ORs were adjusted using either MH or logistic regressions. After methodological quality assessment, 15 case-control studies were marked as being below standards. They provided a total of 207 potentially-biased ORs. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the myriad of pathways of exposure (1117 ORs) than on host specific factors (128) and travel (59) (Figure 5). More information on the distribution of the

number of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 5 by case-control study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio and potential for bias status.

Figure 4. Flow chart of literature search for case-control studies of human salmonellosis
*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

Figure 4. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control studies of *Salmonella* by country (top left), serotype (top right) and population type (bottom)

Figure 5. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control studies of sporadic salmonellosis by design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), risk factor (bottom left) and assigned potential for bias (bottom right)

3.1.2 *Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal- and food-related pathways of transmission*

In most of the meta-analyses conducted on the different data segments, the ORs computed from univariate analysis tended to be lower than those obtained from multivariate analysis (notice that for the meta-analyses on host-specific factors, animal-related pathways, environment-related pathways, person-to-person transmission, and food, meats, eggs and composite consumption pathways, the intercepts for UniOR were negative, reaching statistical significance on some occasions; Tables 4B-11B and 16B). Because of such differences, the meta-analysed ORs were generally expressed in multivariate scale. In all geographical regions, travel is a significant risk factor for salmonellosis, although comparatively in the Asian continent the meta-analysed OR was the lowest (overall OR=1.228; 95% CI: 0.601-2.509; Table 4A). Thus, for the estimation of the travel subcategories, the data points from Asia were removed (Table 4B). Travel abroad for nationals of UK, Netherlands, Canada, USA, Norway, Switzerland and Germany was found to be an important risk factor for acquiring salmonellosis in the combined mixed and children population (overall OR=4.166; 95% CI: 1.712 – 10.13; Table 4B); although before the year 2000, the OR was significantly higher ($p=0.004$). Travel abroad as a risk factor was investigated in sporadic salmonellosis caused by Enteritidis, Typhimurium, Infantis and serogroup BD. Significant difference was found for the pool of individuals travelling inter-state or out of the county within USA and Australia (overall OR=2.517; 95% CI: 0.786 – 8.061). Although the overall OR for travelling abroad seems to be high, international travel may probably represent an underestimated risk factor for sporadic salmonellosis, since *S. Typhimurium* and Enteritidis are common in many of the destination countries with tropical and subtropical climates (Latin America, the Caribbean, Southern Europe and Southeast Asia) and only a fraction of travellers with enteric diseases are identified through routine public health surveillance. In the meta-analysis concerning the travel data partition, only one data point (i.e., OR) was removed (Table 4B). The even distribution of the measured ORs within the funnel plot suggested the absence of publication bias (Figure 6), which was statistically confirmed by the non-significant N (i.e., total number of participants in the case-control study; $p=0.676$), indicating a lack of influence of study size on the measured ORs.

Table 4A. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for *Salmonella* transmission by geographical region for the combined mixed (n=54 ORs) and children (n=4 ORs) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and Children					
Asia	0.206	0.364	4	[-0.508 – 0.920]	0.571
North America	1.481	0.238	19	[1.015 – 1.948]	<.0001
North Europe	1.647	0.414	12	[0.836 – 2.457]	<.0001
Oceania	1.280	0.455	3	[0.388 – 2.171]	0.001
West Europe	1.094	0.270	20	[0.564 – 1.623]	<.0001

Table 4B. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for *Salmonella* transmission for the combined mixed (n=50 ORs) and children (n=4 ORs) population – Asian countries removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
MultiOR					
Travel abroad	1.427 ^a	0.453	47	[0.538 – 2.316]	0.002
Travel inside	0.923 ^b	0.594	4	[-0.241 – 2.087]	0.052
Any travel	0.281 ^c	0.636	4	[-0.965 – 1.528]	0.658
UniOR					
Before 2000	0.586	0.206		[0.182 – 0.990]	0.004
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0868	QE(df=46)		QM(df=3)	
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.3447	p<.001		p<.001	
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0207				
s^2 (residual)	0.8970				
Publication bias	-0.000	-0.000			0.676
Points removed	1				

Figure 6. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for *Salmonella* transmission. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The associations between salmonellosis and host-specific factors from USA and Canada citizens were low for both the mixed population (overall OR=1.944; 95% CI: 1.336 – 2.826) and the children population (overall OR=0.454; 95% CI: 0.110 – 1.881; Table 5A) in

comparison to those from the other regions. For the estimation of the pooled ORs by host-specific subcategories, all geographical regions were included in the analysis. Similarly, the data from both time periods were combined, since there were no significant differences between the ORs from case-control studies conducted before and after the year 2000 in the mixed ($p=0.161$) and the children ($p=0.220$) population (Table 5B).

Table 5A. Meta-analyses of host specific factors for *Salmonella* transmission by region for mixed (n=97) and children (n=27) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	1.250	0.303	13	[0.657 – 1.844]	<.0001
North America	0.665	0.191	43	[0.290 – 1.039]	0.001
North Europe	1.264	0.328	11	[0.620 – 1.907]	<.0001
South America	2.773	1.141	1	[0.531 – 5.010]	0.015
West Europe	1.007	0.223	30	[0.569 – 1.446]	<.0001
Children					
Asia	-1.363	1.381	2	[-4.072 – 1.344]	0.323
North America	-0.788	0.724	8	[-2.207 – 0.632]	0.276
Oceania	0.119	1.406	3	[-2.638 – 2.876]	0.932
West Europe	0.202	0.694	14	[-1.159 – 1.564]	0.771

A host-specific risk factor of similar magnitude to international travel is the use of antimicrobials, antibiotics and anti-diarrhoeal medication up to 4 weeks before onset of salmonellosis in the mixed population (overall OR=5.176; 95% CI: 3.596 – 7.456; Table 5B). Patients of mixed age groups with chronic diseases (namely, allergies, stomach ulcer, cancer, diabetes, endocrine disease, heart disease, kidney disease, intestinal disorders, alcoholism, autoimmune disease and blood disorder) had significantly lower odds of becoming infected with salmonellosis (overall OR=3.597; 95% CI: 2.354 – 5.501), and at the same level of odds were those patients receiving other medications such as NSAID, corticosteroids, thyroid and hormone drugs (overall OR=3.034; 95% CI: 2.106 – 4.375). Among the host-specific risk factors for salmonellosis in the mixed population, the lowest odds were borne by the patients in use of anti-acids (H₂ receptor antagonists and proton pump inhibitors) up to 30 days before the onset of disease (overall OR=2.335; 95% CI: 1.621 – 3.364). When focusing on infants and children, the use of anti-acids (overall OR=3.350; 95% CI: 1.838 – 6.104) and antibiotics (overall OR=2.648; 95% CI: 1.813 – 3.865) produced a similar degree of risk of salmonellosis, although the data points available for the former were too few (only 3) to draw any conclusion. In the population of infants, breastfeeding was proven to be protective against *Salmonella* infection by decreasing the odds of illness by ~3.5. Combining the results from seven case-control studies, 747 infants of age lower than 2 years had on average 0.285 (95% CI: 0.209 – 0.389) times the odds of becoming ill than those who were not breastfed. In the two meta-analyses on host-specific factors for children and mixed population, no data points

were removed after assessment of influential points by Cook's distance (Table 5B). Funnel plots of both meta-analyses did not imply any strong evidence of publication bias (Figure 7), which was confirmed statistically by the non-significant effect of study size on the reported ORS ($p=0.607$ for mixed population and $p=0.128$ for children population; Table 5B).

Table 5B. Meta-analyses of host specific factors for *Salmonella* transmission for mixed (n=96) and children (n=27) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Antiacids	0.848 ^a	0.186	31	[0.483 – 1.213]	<.0001
	Antibiotics	1.644 ^c	0.185	34	[1.280 – 2.009]	<.0001
	Chronic	1.280 ^b	0.216	20	[0.856 – 1.705]	<.0001
	Other Med	1.110 ^b	0.186	11	[0.745 – 1.476]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.324	0.179		[-0.675 – 0.020]	0.070
	Before 2000					0.161
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2265	QE(df=89)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0173	$p<.001$		$p<.001$	
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0129				
	s^2 (residual)	0.6883				
	Publication bias	-0.000	-0.000			0.607
	Points removed	0				
Children	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Antiacids	1.209 ^b	0.306	3	[0.609 – 1.809]	<.0001
	Antibiotics	0.974 ^b	0.193	12	[0.595 – 1.352]	<.0001
	Breastfed	-1.255 ^a	0.159	12	[-1.566 - -0.943]	<.0001
	UniOR	-0.172	0.188		[-0.541 – 0.197]	0.362
	Before 2000					0.220
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=23)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.4822	$p=0.143$		$p<.001$	
	Publication bias	-0.001	0.001			0.128
	Points removed	0				

Figure 7. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of host-specific risk factors for *Salmonella* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The contact with animals and people, especially by children and immunosuppressed people, can result in human salmonellosis. Animals commonly infected with *Salmonella* serovars which may pose a risk to humans include farm animals, amphibians, birds, cats, dogs, fish, guinea pigs, hamsters, mice, rabbits, lizards, snakes and turtles. Regardless of the geographical region, it was found that the risk of disease in children was higher (overall OR 2.450 – 5.590) than in the mixed population (overall OR 1.528 – 1.749; Table 6A). However, as the animal routes of exposure seemed to pose a lower risk of salmonellosis (overall OR=1.271) in Asia than in the other geographical regions, the observations from the Asian region were removed from the animal routes data set partition. Since the time period at which the case-control study was conducted did not influence the overall ORs ($p=0.314$ in the mixed population and $p=0.483$ in the children population), this covariate was removed from the meta-analyses (Table 6B). In the mixed population, contact and/or ownership of pets increased the odds of contracting salmonellosis (overall OR=1.983; 95% CI: 1.569 – 2.506) as much as contact with wild animals, such as native animals, birds, wild mammals, snake, reptiles and rodents, farm animals (overall OR=1.974; 95% CI: 1.473 – 2.649). Occupational exposure to animals, by being a farmer, a fieldworker, a fisherman or a slaughterhouse worker, presented on average the highest level of risk (overall OR=2.583; 95% CI: 1.793 – 3.718), whereas contact with farm animals, conveyed a risk of disease (overall OR=1.752; 95% CI: 1.277– 2.404) slightly lower than did exposure to pets and wild animals. In children, the overall risks due to contact with animals were significantly higher than in the mixed population. Children that had contact with pets at home had on average higher risks of salmonellosis than those who did not (overall OR=3.155; 95% CI: 1.954 – 5.089), and was not significantly different from the mean risk due to contact with wild animals (overall OR=3.043; 95% CI: 1.690 – 5.485). Among the animal contact's routes of transmission, direct contact with farm animals was found to bear the highest risk of salmonellosis in children (overall OR=5.977; 95% CI: 2.793 – 12.79). These results are not unexpected since children are less likely to be careful with hand hygiene during and after a farm visit, and they may have also less immunity to the pathogens potentially transmitted through direct contact, as they are in general expected to be exposed to farm animals infrequently. No publication

bias was evident since in the meta-analysis on animal contact pathways as risk factors for salmonellosis: there was no association between study size and measured ORs ($p=0.857$ in the mixed population and $p=0.628$ in the children population; Table 6B), which was also graphically suggested by the funnel plots (Figure 8). The assessment of Cook's distance led to the removal of two potentially-biased ORs and one potentially-biased OR in the meta-analyses for the mixed and children population, respectively (Table 6B).

Table 6A. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for *Salmonella*-transmission by region in the mixed (n=132) and children (n=45) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.240	0.345	4	[-0.437 – 0.918]	0.487
North America	0.475	0.161	61	[0.157 – 0.792]	0.003
North Europe	0.424	0.245	16	[-0.057 – 0.906]	0.084
Oceania	0.559	0.279	23	[0.012 – 1.107]	0.045
West Europe	0.445	0.236	28	[-0.018 – 0.909]	0.059
Children					
North America	0.896	0.322	14	[0.264 – 1.528]	0.005
Oceania	1.721	0.802	2	[0.147 – 3.295]	0.032
West Europe	1.055	0.359	29	[0.350 – 1.760]	0.003

Figure 8. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of animal contact pathways as risk factors for *Salmonella* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 6B. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for *Salmonella*-transmission in the mixed (n=128) and children (n=45) population – Asian countries removed from the mixed population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
		Farm	0.561 ^a	0.161	20	[0.245 – 0.877]	<.0001
		Occupational	0.949 ^c	0.185	12	[0.584 – 1.313]	<.0001
		Pets	0.685 ^b	0.119	71	[0.451 – 0.919]	<.0001
		Wild	0.680 ^b	0.149	25	[0.387– 0.974]	0.018
		UniOR	-0.274	0.081		[-0.433 – -0.114]	<.0001
		Before 2000					0.314
	Random effects						
		s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2245	QE(df=120)		QM(df=4)	
		s ² (residual)	0.5811	p<.001		p<.001	
		Publication bias	0.000	0.000			0.857
		Points removed	3				
	Children	Fixed effects					
MultiOR							
		Farm	1.788 ^a	0.388	5	[1.027 – 2.549]	<.0001
		Pets	1.149 ^a	0.244	37	[0.670 – 1.627]	<.0001
		Wild	1.113 ^a	0.300	3	[0.525 – 1.702]	0.001
		UniOR	-0.085	0.126		[-0.333 – 0.162]	0.497
		Before 2000					0.483
Random effects							
		s ² _u (Intercept)	0.3137	QE(df=40)		QM(df=3)	
		s ² (residual)	0.512	p=0.005		p<.001	
		Publication bias	0.0003	0.0005			0.628
		Points removed	1				

The meta-analysis on the environmental routes of transmission by region produced pooled ORs in the children population (2.945 – 10.196) from North America, Northern Europe, Western Europe and Oceania that were considerably higher than those in the mixed population (1.640 – 2.688; Table 7A). Since the overall OR for Asia (2.050) was within this range (i.e., level of risk), this data was not removed for the subcategory meta-analysis. In the mixed population, the most risky environmental transmission routes were related to water, either by drinking untreated or non-disinfected water, private well water or water from surface sources (overall OR=2.989; 95% CI: 1.680 – 5.317; Table 7B) or by exposure to recreational

water, including contact with sea, lakes, rivers and swamps, and practising water sports (overall OR=2.408; 95% CI: 1.331 – 4.362). The meta-analysis in this category indicated that living on or visiting a farm or rural environment poses a significantly lower risk of salmonellosis infection (overall OR=1.900; 95% CI: 0.983 – 3.677), which is comparable to the transmission via contact with farm animals (overall OR=1.752; 95% CI: 1.277 – 2.404; Table 7B).

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of environment pathways for *Salmonella* transmission by region for mixed (n=58) and children (n=30) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.719	0.209	12	[0.308 – 1.131]	0.001
North America	0.634	0.211	17	[0.219 – 1.048]	0.003
North Europe	0.497	0.261	12	[-0.015 – 1.010]	0.057
Oceania	0.560	0.274	11	[0.023 – 1.097]	0.041
West Europe	0.989	0.445	6	[-0.116 – 1.862]	0.026
Children					
North America	1.080	0.303	13	[0.487 – 1.673]	0.001
North Europe	2.322	1.234	1	[-0.097 – 4.742]	0.060
Oceania	1.102	0.810	1	[-0.486 – 2.690]	0.174
West Europe	0.661	0.310	15	[0.053 – 1.270]	0.033

Figure 9. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of environmental pathways as risk factors for *Salmonella* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of environment pathways for *Salmonella* transmission for mixed (n=56) and children (n=28) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Drink water	1.095 ^a	0.294	25	[0.519 – 1.671]	0.002
	Farm	0.642 ^b	0.336	16	[-0.017 – 1.302]	0.056
	Rec. water	0.879 ^a	0.303	15	[0.286– 1.473]	0.004
	UniOR	-0.283	0.332		[-0.934 – 0.368]	0.394
	Before 2000					0.156
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1880	QE(df=52)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0911	p<.001		p<.001	
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0240				
	s^2 (residual)	0.6102				
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000			0.056
	Points removed	2				
	Children	Fixed effects				
MultiOR						
Day care		1.197 ^a	0.302	10	[0.569 – 1.825]	<.0001
Drink water		1.179 ^a	0.339	7	[0.515 – 1.843]	<.0001
Playground		1.294 ^a	0.254	11	[0.796 – 1.792]	<.0001
UniOR		-0.651	0.375		[-1.386 – 0.084]	0.082
Before 2000						0.335
Random effects						
s^2_u (Intercept)		0.0000	QE(df=23)		QM(df=3)	
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)		0.0902	p=0.454		p=0.080	
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)		0.0429				
s^2 (residual)		0.2730				
Publication bias		0.0005	0.0003			0.105
Points removed		1				

As occurred in the previous meta-analyses on animal contact's routes of transmission, for the environmental routes of transmission, the children population also displayed higher mean ORs than the mixed population. However, within the children population, there were no statistical differences in risk among the pathways: day care attendance, drinking untreated water and playground; although at least numerically, the mean OR of children through

playgrounds was higher than the other two classes. The playground pathway, encompassing the exposures: visit to parks, touching soil, playing in sandbox, fetching objects from ground to mouth and child’s handling of raw meat while in shopping cart, produced an overall OR of 3.647 (95% CI: 2.217 – 6.000). Interestingly, children that attended a day care centre, crèche, (overall OR=3.310; 95% CI: 1.766 – 6.203) turned out to be as exposed to salmonellosis as those who drank untreated water (overall OR=3.251; 95% CI: 1.674 – 6.315). No effect of case-control study’s time period was found in any of the studied populations, mixed (p=0.155) and children (p=0.335; Table 7B). In the assessment of influential data points, two potentially-biased ORs were removed from the mixed population data set while one potentially-biased OR was removed from the children data set in the meta-analyses for environmental routes of transmission. The statistical analysis for publication bias indicated that there could be some publication bias in the overall OR estimates for the mixed population (p=0.056; Table 7B). However, the corresponding funnel plot (Figure 9; left) suggested the presence of only a minor asymmetry in the distribution of data points.

An important route for acquiring salmonellosis is through contagion from an infected person. Bringing together information from North America, Northern Europe, Western Europe and Oceania, the person-to-person overall risk of transmission was significant, in the range of 1.150 – 3.300 (Table 8A). Since the overall risk for the Asian population (2.921) was within the above range, the ORs measures produced in these countries were included in the analysis. In the mixed population, having contact with an ill person or a patient, having a person with diarrhoea in the household or an elderly in diapers in the household bear a mean odds of acquiring salmonellosis of 2.479 (95% CI: 1.197 – 5.140; Table 8B). In children, the person-to-person route of transmission poses a significantly higher risk at an overall OR of 4.000 (95% CI: 1.815 – 8.802). Statistically, there was no influence of the time period in which the case-control study was conducted (before or after the year 2000) on the observed ORs (p=0.838; Table 8B); hence the year category covariate was dropped from the model. In this meta-analytical data partition, one potentially-biased OR was removed after Cook’s distance assessment (Table 8B). Although the corresponding funnel plot showed some minor asymmetry (Figure 10), statistically, study size did not affect the overall ORs (p=0.125).

Table 8A. Meta-analysis of person-to-person pathway for *Salmonella* transmission by region for the combined mixed (n=15) and children (n=9) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children					
Asia	1.072	0.446	5	[0.198 – 1.945]	0.017
North America	0.961	0.372	7	[0.231 – 1.691]	0.010
North Europe	0.140	0.693	1	[-1.218 – 1.497]	0.840
Oceania	0.776	0.588	3	[-0.376 – 1.927]	0.187
West Europe	1.194	0.390	8	[0.429 – 1.957]	0.002

Table 8B. Meta-analysis of person-to-person pathway for *Salmonella* transmission for the combined mixed (n=15) and children (n=9) population – no geographical region removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
MultiOR					
Children	1.386 ^b	0.403	9	[0.596 – 2.175]	<.0001
Mixed	0.908 ^a	0.372	15	[0.180– 1.637]	0.014
UniOR	-0.091	0.327		[-0.732 – 0.550]	0.780
Before 2000					0.838
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3316	QE(df=17)		QM(df=2)	
s^2 (residual)	0.7097	p<.001		p=0.002	
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000			0.125
Points removed	1				

Figure 10. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of person-to-person pathway for *Salmonella* transmission in the combined mixed and children population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Ingestion of contaminated food represented a significant risk factor for salmonellosis which was higher in children from North America, Western Europe and Oceania (overall ORs: 1.929 – 3.568) than in the mixed population from the same regions (overall ORs: 0.987 – 1.687; Table 9A). In the mixed populations of Asia (overall OR=1.501) and South America (overall OR=1.444), the levels of risk posed by foods were within the order of those of North America and Western Europe. For this reason, the OR measures estimated in countries of Asia and South America were not removed for the subcategory meta-analysis.

Table 9A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for *Salmonella* transmission by region for mixed (n=596) and children (n=85) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.406	0.190	46	[0.033 – 0.778]	0.033
North America	0.408	0.116	231	[0.180 – 0.635]	<.0001
North Europe	0.523	0.158	135	[0.214 – 0.833]	0.001
Oceania	-0.013	0.262	14	[-0.527 – 0.501]	0.962
South America	0.368	0.516	15	[-0.643 – 1.379]	0.475
West Europe	0.384	0.192	155	[0.008 – 0.761]	0.045
Children					
Asia	1.447	0.611	1	[0.248 – 2.645]	0.017
North America	0.733	0.154	23	[0.429 – 1.035]	<.0001
Oceania	1.272	0.410	3	[0.467 – 2.076]	0.002
West Europe	0.657	0.144	56	[0.374 – 0.939]	<.0001

Despite the strong link between food of animal origin and human salmonellosis, this meta-analysis has underscored that people may be infected by ingesting other foods such as produce and beverages. In the mixed population, the highest mean OR measuring association between illness and food consumption was observed for the food category Eggs. It can be said that, overall, the ill cases appeared to have consumed eggs and eggs products more frequently than controls (OR=2.575; 95% CI: 2.132 – 3.111; Table 9B). This overall OR combined the observed risks from a great variety of egg preparations such as scrambled, fried, boiled and pouched eggs, both ways of consumption – well-cooked and undercooked/raw – as well as eggs products such as mayonnaise. The relative importance of this food category is congruent with current outbreak data; as only in 2015, eggs and egg products contaminated with *Salmonella* serovars were responsible for 21.2% of the strong-evidence outbreaks in the EU (EFSA, 2016), the second most important food vehicle after meat and meat products. The second most important food transmission route in the mixed population, according to this meta-analysis, was through the consumption of meat and meat products with an overall OR of 2.305 (95% CI: 1.912 – 2.782). Such mean OR summarised the association of the consumption of raw, undercooked and well-done poultry meat, red meats, RTE meats, BBQ meats and meat processed products. With regards to outbreaks in the EU, the meat categories all together (meat and meat products, pig meat, broiler meat and turkey) were causative agents of 31.9% of the strong-evidence outbreaks in 2015, representing the most important route for *Salmonella* transmission (EFSA, 2016). While beverages (mostly represented by fruit juices; overall OR=2.008; 95% CI: 1.504 – 2.686) and composite or multi-ingredient food (overall OR=2.147; 95% CI: 1.756 – 2.625) apparently provided a similar level of salmonellosis risk for consumers, some caution should be taken when interpreting the result for the beverages category as it combined only 8 ORs. It is worthy to mention that the composite food category was made up of 90% of exposures belonging to the setting Eating Out, which by itself may represent another risk factor (i.e., as opposed to food prepared at home). In terms of outbreaks, multi-ingredient foods (taking buffet meals and composite food together) was the

third most important food vehicle of transmission, accounting for 12.5% of the strong-evidence outbreaks in the EU in 2015 (EFSA, 2016).

Table 9B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for *Salmonella* transmission for mixed (n=596) and children (n=85) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
		Beverages	0.697 ^b	0.148	8	[0.408 – 0.988]	<.0001
		Composite	0.764 ^b	0.103	82	[0.563 – 0.965]	<.0001
		Dairy	0.648 ^{ab}	0.107	40	[0.439 – 0.857]	<.0001
		Eggs	0.946 ^d	0.097	140	[0.757 – 1.135]	<.0001
		Meat	0.835 ^c	0.096	231	[0.648 – 1.023]	<.0001
		Produce	0.612 ^a	0.100	81	[0.416 – 0.808]	<.0001
		Seafood	0.587 ^a	0.123	14	[0.347 – 0.828]	<.0001
		UniOR	-0.553	0.096		[-0.742 – -0.364]	<.0001
		Before 2000					0.989
	Random effects						
		s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1889	QE(df=584)		QM(df=7)	
		s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0079	p<.001		p<.001	
		s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0512				
		s^2 (residual)	0.7560				
		Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000		0.002	
		Points removed	4				
	Children/ Infants	Fixed effects					
		MultiOR					
		Dairy	1.049 ^b	0.186	10	[0.684 – 1.415]	<.0001
		Eggs	0.603 ^a	0.151	22	[0.307 – 0.899]	<.0001
		Meat	0.733 ^{ab}	0.139	36	[0.459 – 1.006]	<.0001
		Produce	0.681 ^a	0.160	13	[0.367 – 0.996]	<.0001
		Seafood	1.027 ^b	0.368	4	[0.304 – 1.750]	0.005
		UniOR	-0.008	0.110		[-0.224 – 0.208]	0.941
		Before 2000					0.210
Random effects							
		s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0535	QE(df=77)		QM(df=5)	
		s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0083	p=0.054		p<.0001	
		s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0002				

s^2 (residual)	0.4696		
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0003	0.372
Points removed	2		

Dairy foods, produce and seafood were the food categories with the lowest mean risk of salmonellosis, and meta-analysed ORs were not statistically different among them. The dairy food vehicles recovered from case-control studies were mostly raw milk and cheese made of unpasteurised milk (overall OR=1.912; 95% CI: 1.551 – 2.356), while the produce-related exposures encompassed the consumption of fresh vegetables, leafy greens, fruits, sprouts, nuts and RTE salads (overall OR=1.844; 95% CI: 1.516 – 2.243). The exposures related to seafood consumption most frequently extracted were fish, smoked fish, shrimps and shellfish, which produced an overall OR of 1.799 (95% CI: 1.415 – 2.289). Accordingly, when comparing to EU outbreak data, contaminated fish (2.7%) and vegetables (1.6%) were the least frequent causative agent of the strong-evidence outbreaks of salmonellosis in 2015 (EFSA, 2016). Interestingly, the meta-analysed risks of sporadic salmonellosis by food class association follow a pattern similar to the contributions of each food class to the total number of EU outbreaks of salmonellosis in 2015. The trend depicted in Figure 11 is of referential value since meta-analysed ORs included case-control studies conducted worldwide since 1987 while outbreak data belong to EU member states only for 2015.

Figure 11. A comparison between the meta-analysed odds-ratios for sporadic salmonellosis by food category and the percentage of strong-evidence outbreaks in the EU in 2015

In the children population, the meta-analysis on food classes revealed that exposures via milk and milk formula can represent a high risk for infants to acquire salmonellosis (overall OR=2.855; 95% CI: 1.982 – 4.116). The consumption of fish and shrimps by children (overall OR=2.793; 95% CI: 1.355 – 5.755) is seemingly a pathway of exposure as important as dairy. In the second place lay the food class meat with an overall OR=2.081 (95%: 1.582 – 2.735) as a product of combining exposures such as beef, pork, ground beef/pork, chicken and sausages, both eaten at home and outside. Although at a lower level of risk, both eggs (overall OR=1.828; 95% CI: 1.359 – 2.457) and produce (represented by salad vegetables; overall OR=1.976; 95% CI: 1.443 – 2.707) bear still a significant risk for transmission of *Salmonella* sp. in children. In these general meta-analyses encompassing all foods, there was no significant difference in the OR outcomes from older (< year 2000) and recent (>2000) case-

control studies, either in the mixed population ($p=0.989$) or in the children population ($p=0.208$; Table 9B). In terms of publication bias, for the meta-analysis performed on the mixed population, some under-reporting of non-significant ORs may be present ($p=0.002$) whereas for the children population there is no strong evidence of under-reporting ($p=0.372$; Table 9). The funnel plots for the meta-analyses associated to food exposures are displayed in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food pathways for *Salmonella* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

By consuming meat, children in North America and Western Europe were more susceptible to become infected with salmonellosis (overall ORs: 1.570 – 2.307) than the mixed population from North America, Oceania and Europe (overall ORs: 1.016 – 1.443; Table 10A). As case-studies conducted in South America produced a very low overall OR (0.700), not being within the above overall OR range, those data points in addition to the only one from an Asian case-control study (Table 10A) were removed in the subsequent meta-analysis on meat subcategories. In the general meta-analysis, there were not significant differences in OR values associated to meat consumption between early and recent case-control studies in the mixed population ($p=0.576$; Table 10B). The time period did not have any influence either in the poultry subclass ($p=0.881$) or in the pork subclass ($p=0.202$) when assessed separately (full meta-analyses not shown). The consumption of pork meat presented the highest association with salmonellosis (overall OR=2.662; 95% CI: 2.075 – 3.418; Table 10B), followed by the subclasses Other Meats (overall OR=2.459; 95% CI: 1.915 – 3.152) and Other Red Meats (overall OR=2.442; 95% CI: 1.640 – 3.363). Both meat subclasses comprised undefined red meat, BBQ meats, sheep, lamb, mutton, venison and wild game meat. Thus, it is important to continue educating consumers about the risk of eating undercooked pork and red meats as well as game meat. At a lower level of risk, differing statistically from pork meat, laid poultry meat (overall OR=2.181; 95% CI: 1.728 – 2.754). The meat subcategories with the lowest mean risks of salmonellosis were beef (overall OR: 1.674; 95% CI: 1.266 – 2.151), followed by processed meats (overall OR=1.868; 95% CI: 1.487 – 2.346) – with exposures to products such as meat paste, burgers, sausages, hotdogs, cold meats and bacon. In the meat consumption meta-analysis for the mixed population, two potentially-biased ORs were removed. In addition, there was no statistical evidence of publication bias ($p=0.173$; Table 10B), which was also implied by the satisfactory spread of observations within the funnel plot (Figure 13, left).

Table 10A. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for *Salmonella*-transmission by region for mixed (n=231) and children (n=30) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	-0.073	0.634	1	[-1.316 – 1.171]	0.908
North America	0.299	0.137	83	[0.029 – 0.569]	0.030
North Europe	0.367	0.179	73	[0.015 – 0.718]	0.041
Oceania	0.016	0.444	3	[-0.855 – 0.886]	0.972
South America	-0.350	0.646	4	[-1.617 – 0.916]	0.587
West Europe	0.263	0.233	67	[-0.193 – 0.719]	0.259
Children					
North America	0.455	0.270	8	[-0.075 – 0.985]	0.093
West Europe	0.836	0.191	22	[0.460 – 1.211]	<.0001

The relative importance of the meat subcategories in the children population has a different landscape from that seen in the mixed population. In children, pork (overall OR=3.193; 95% CI: 1.946 – 5.244) and beef meat (overall OR=2.782; 95% CI: 1.793 – 4.315) were estimated to be the most important pathways for salmonellosis within the large group of meat. The consumption of chicken sausage and Mettwurst pork sausage (only exposures in Processed Meats for children) ranked second with an overall OR of 1.839 (95% CI: 1.269 – 2.662) while the exposure to chicken, deli chicken and any poultry ranked third in relative importance with an overall OR=1.438 (95% CI: 1.060 – 1.950). In the meta-analysis of meat consumption for children, no influential observations were found, so all points were kept for analysis (Table 10B). While the test for publication bias hinted some effect of study size on the measured ORs ($p=0.060$; Table 10B), the graphical display showed an even distribution of points within the funnel space (Figure 13, right).

Figure 13. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of meat consumption pathways for *Salmonella* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 10B. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for *Salmonella*-transmission for mixed (n=226) and children (n=30) population – Asia and South America removed from the mixed population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
	Beef	0.515 ^a	0.128	26	[0.236 – 0.766]	<.0001	
	Other red meat	0.893 ^c	0.203	10	[0.495 – 1.291]	<.0001	
	Others	0.900 ^c	0.127	20	[0.650 – 1.148]	<.0001	
	Pork	0.979 ^c	0.127	19	[0.730 – 1.229]	<.0001	
	Poultry	0.745 ^b	0.111	93	[0.527 – 0.963]	<.0001	
	Proc meat	0.625 ^a	0.116	58	[0.397 – 0.853]	<.0001	
	UniOR	-0.538	0.103		[-0.739 – -0.337]	<.0001	
	Before 2000					0.576	
	Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2121	QE(df=219)		QM(df=6)		
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0004	p<.001		p<.001		
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0108					
	s^2 (residual)	0.7460					
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000				0.173	
Points removed	2						
Children/ Infants	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
	Beef	1.023 ^c	0.224	10	[0.584 – 1.462]	<.0001	
	Pork	1.161 ^c	0.253	4	[0.666 – 1.657]	<.0001	
	Poultry	0.363 ^a	0.155	11	[0.058 – 0.668]	0.019	
	Proc meat	0.609 ^b	0.189	5	[0.238 – 0.979]	0.001	
	UniOR	-0.055	0.258		[-0.562 – 0.451]	0.829	
	Before 2000					0.160	
	Random effects						
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0131	QE(df=25)		QM(df=4)		
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.1569	p=0.029		p<0.001		
	s^2 (residual)	0.6000					
	Publication bias	-0.0013	0.0007				0.060
	Points removed	0					

In the egg-class meta-analysis by geographical region, the mixed populations from North America, Europe and Oceania presented levels of associations between risk of salmonellosis and consumption of eggs (overall ORs: 1.01 – 1.827) similar to those of the children cases from North America and Western Europe (overall ORs: 1.423 – 1.560; Table 11A). For the subcategory meta-analysis, the observations from South America were removed since their pooled OR (4.071) was significantly higher than the others. In the general meta-analyses for both the mixed and the children population, ORs from older case-control studies (before 2000) were significantly higher than those from 2000 onwards. Thus, in Table 11B, the overall ORs for eggs and egg products are expressed on the basis of the recent case-control studies, while the intercept “Before 2000” indicates by how much the overall log OR is increased in the older case-control studies. Within the eggs class, the consumption of egg products was as important a risk factor (overall OR=2.906; 95% CI: 1.268 – 6.652) as eggs (overall OR=2.115; 95% CI: 0.949 – 4.641) as vehicle of transmission of *Salmonella* spp. in the mixed population (Table 11B). In the children population, no exposures related to egg products were found in the primary studies, yet the consumption of raw, undercooked and cooked eggs amounted to an overall OR of 1.484 (95% CI: 1.167 – 1.889). Statistically, in the meta-analyses on eggs consumption, the reported ORs were not affected by study size either in the mixed population ($p=0.424$) or in the children population ($p=0.644$; Table 11B), although the funnel plot of the former (Figure 14, left) showed some lack of OR outcomes to the left side. This may arise from the type of exposure question often posed when enquiring about eggs, namely: raw eggs, undercooked eggs, runny eggs, sunny side-up eggs, soft-boiled eggs and eggs with runny whites; this is, exposures that are a priori known to have higher ORs. Thus, small size studies that managed to obtain high and significant OR tend to be reported, while small size studies that did not will remain unpublished.

Table 11A. Meta-analyses of eggs consumption related pathways for *Salmonella*-transmission by region for mixed (n=140) and children (n=19) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.581	0.617	2	[-0.629 – 1.790]	0.347
North America	0.470	0.150	71	[0.175 – 0.765]	0.002
North Europe	0.475	0.233	30	[0.018 – 0.931]	0.041
Oceania	0.010	0.635	2	[-1.234 – 1.254]	0.988
South America	1.404	0.673	7	[0.085 – 2.722]	0.037
West Europe	0.603	0.244	28	[0.123 – 1.082]	0.014
Children					
North America	0.353	0.289	3	[-0.214 – 0.919]	0.222
West Europe	0.445	0.149	16	[0.152 – 0.737]	0.003

Table 11B. Meta-analyses of eggs consumption related pathways for *Salmonella*-transmission for mixed (n=131) and children (n=19) population – Asian and South American countries removed from the mixed population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	Fixed effects					
	MultiOR					
	Eggs	0.749 ^a	0.408	115	[-0.052 – 1.535]	0.067
	Egg prods	1.067 ^b	0.426	16	[0.238 – 1.895]	0.011
	UniOR	-0.527	0.387		[-1.286 – 0.232]	0.174
	Before 2000	0.292	0.193		[-0.086 – 0.670]	0.131
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2395	QE(df=127)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.2558	p<.001		p=0.002	
	s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0001				
	s^2 (residual)	0.7759				
	Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.424
	Points removed	0				
	Children/ Infants	Fixed effects				
MultiOR						
Eggs		0.395	0.122	19	[0.155 – 0.636]	0.001
UniOR		-0.030	0.142		[-0.308 – 0.247]	0.831
Before 2000		0.413	0.261		[-0.098 – 0.925]	0.113
Random effects						
s^2_u (Intercept)		0.0001	QE(df=15)			
s^2 (residual)		0.1719	p=0.924			
Publication bias		0.0002	0.0004			0.644
Points removed		1				

Looking into the dairy foods (Table 12A), their association with salmonellosis in the mixed population exhibited a large variation (overall ORs: 0.787 – 4.297) depending upon the geographical region. While the lowest overall OR belonged to the cases from Western Europe (overall OR=0.787) and North America (overall OR=0.910), all the geographical regions were included in the analysis given the few data points available. There were no significant differences in the meta-analysed ORs of salmonellosis due to the consumption of cheese (overall OR=0.852; 95% CI: 0.417 – 1.738), dairy-origin fats (overall OR=0.892; 95% CI: 0.400 – 1.991) and milk (overall OR=0.806; 95% CI: 0.399 – 1.629) in the mixed population, and they appeared as less important transmission routes of *Salmonella* spp. (Table 12B). However, the exposure to powder infant formula was the most important transmission route in children (overall OR=2.300; 95% CI: 1.679 – 3.152) among all dairy classes. Neither in the

mixed population ($p=0.420$) nor in the children population meta-analysis ($p=0.745$), there was statistical difference in the measured outcomes between the older and more recent case-control studies. After Cook's distance assessment, only one OR value was discarded from the meta-analysis on dairy classes in mixed, while no statistical evidence of publication bias was found either in the mixed population ($p=0.116$) or in the children population ($p=0.348$; Table 12B). The corresponding funnel plots are shown in Figure 15.

Figure 14. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of eggs consumption pathways for *Salmonella* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 12A. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for *Salmonella* transmission by region for mixed ($n=35$) and children ($n=8$) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.433	0.230	6	[-0.017 – 0.885]	0.059
North America	-0.094	0.186	14	[-0.458 – 0.269]	0.610
North Europe	1.458	0.786	1	[-0.082 – 2.999]	0.063
South America	0.338	0.566	2	[-0.772 – 1.448]	0.550
West Europe	-0.239	0.211	12	[-0.654 – 0.175]	0.258
Children					
Asia	1.447	0.627	1	[0.216 – 2.677]	0.021
North America	0.973	0.253	5	[0.477 – 1.468]	<.0001
Oceania	1.775	0.484	2	[0.826 – 2.723]	<.0001

Table 12B. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for *Salmonella* transmission for mixed (n=35) and children (n=8) population – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
		Cheese	-0.160 ^a	0.364	14	[-0.874 – 0.553]	0.659
		Fats	-0.114 ^a	0.410	10	[-0.917 – 0.689]	0.782
		Milk	-0.216 ^a	0.359	11	[-0.920 – 0.488]	0.548
		UniOR	0.126	0.389		[-0.636– 0.889]	0.745
		Before 2000					0.420
	Random effects						
		s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0031	QE(df=30)		QM(df=3)	
		s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0956	p<.0001		p=0.779	
		s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.2166				
		s^2 (residual)	0.5127				
		Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.116
		Points removed	1				
	Children/ Infants	Fixed effects					
MultiOR							
		Powder	0.833	0.161	8	[0.518 – 1.148]	<.0001
		UniOR	0.657	0.315		[0.040 – 1.275]	0.037
		Before 2000					0.745
Random effects							
		s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=6)			
		s^2 (residual)	0.2392	p=0.505			
		Publication bias	-0.0005	0.0005			0.348
		Points removed	0				

The meta-analysis on risk of salmonellosis due to seafood by geographical region is shown in Table 13A. Due to the limited number of ORs available from the case-control studies, it was not possible to make any inference on the differences among geographical regions. All extracted data points, regardless of the region, were used in the general meta-analysis on seafood subcategories. The year category of the case-control study could not be proved to have any influence on measured risk (p=0.668; Table 13B). It was found that neither fish (overall OR=0.682; 95% CI: 0.384 – 1.210) nor processed seafood (overall OR=0.885; 95% CI: 0.343 – 2.284) convey to the mixed population a significant risk of acquiring salmonellosis. Although meta-analysis was performed only on three reported ORs, the consumption of shellfish by the mixed population represented a more important risk factor for

salmonellosis at an estimated overall OR of 1.387 (95% CI: 0.662 – 2.906). At a higher level of risk laid fish and crustaceans consumed by the children population (overall OR=1.704; 95% CI: 0.507 – 5.726). No potentially-biased estimates were removed from the seafood-pathway meta-analyses. For the mixed population, there was no strong evidence of publication bias ($p=0.369$; Table 13 and Figure 16, left). Although, for the children population, the statistical analysis hinted the presence of some bias ($p=0.011$; Table 13B), the funnel plot (Figure 16, right) suggested that the spread of ORs was acceptable considering that only four ORs were found for this seafood category.

Figure 15. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for *Salmonella* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 13A. Meta-analyses of seafood-related pathways for *Salmonella* transmission by region for the mixed (n=13) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.248	0.311	3	[-0.362 – 0.858]	0.425
North America	-0.305	0.332	2	[-0.956 – 0.347]	0.358
South America	-0.693	0.628	1	[-1.924 – 0.538]	0.270
West Europe	-0.220	0.268	7	[-0.746 – 0.305]	0.411

Table 13B. Meta-analyses of seafood-related pathways for *Salmonella* transmission for mixed (n=13) and children (n=4) population – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
		Fish	-0.382 ^a	0.293	7	[-0.956 – 0.191]	0.191
		Shellfish	0.327 ^b	0.378	3	[-0.413 – 1.067]	0.386
		Processed	-0.122 ^a	0.484	3	[-1.070 – 0.826]	0.801
		UniOR	0.025	0.305		[-0.572 – 0.622]	0.935
		Before 2000					0.668
	Random effects						
		s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0906	QE(df=9)		QM(df=3)	
		s^2 (residual)	0.2370	p=0.020		p=0.169	
	Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0001			0.369	
	Points removed	0					
Children/ Infants	Fixed effects						
		Fish/Crustac	0.533	0.619	4	[-0.679 – 1.745]	0.388
		Before 2000					ND
	Random effects						
		s^2_u (Intercept)	0.6497	QE(df=3)			
		s^2 (residual)	0.5240	p=0.078			
		Publication bias	0.0015	0.0006			0.011
	Points removed	0					

ND: The effect of time period could not be tested due to the limited number of data points

Figure 16. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of seafood consumption pathways for *Salmonella* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

In the meta-analysis on salmonellosis risk attributed to produce by region (Table 14A, the case-control studies conducted in the Asian countries presented an overall OR (1.944) higher than those of the other regions (pooled ORs: 1.000 – 1.410). Thus, for the analysis by produce subcategory, the Asian case-control studies were removed from the mixed population data set. Among the produce subcategories (i.e., fruits, nuts, roots, fresh vegetables and vegetable products), there was not a single class that *statistically* differed from the others in terms of risk of salmonellosis posed to the mixed population (QM test, $p=0.261$; Table 14B). Numerically, however, fruits (overall OR=1.085; 95% CI: 0.663 – 1.781) and fresh vegetables (overall OR=1.051; 95% CI: 0.654 – 1.690) were on average more associated to disease than nuts (overall OR=0.924; 95% CI: 0.558 – 1.534), roots (overall OR=0.966; 95% CI: 0.536 – 1.742) and vegetable products (overall OR=0.902; 95% CI: 0.540 – 1.504). Nonetheless, a higher risk of salmonellosis was associated with children when they consumed leafy greens, tomatoes and herbs (overall OR=2.000; 95% CI: 0.806 – 4.963). Although the funnel plots for the seafood-pathway meta-analyses revealed the existence of some publication bias (Figure 17), the statistical test did not find a significant effect of study size on our observation of the effect size ($p=0.294$ for the mixed population and $p=0.875$ for the children population; Table 14B).

Table 14A. Meta-analyses of produce consumption related pathways for *Salmonella* transmission by region for mixed (n=79) and children (n=10) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	0.665	0.349	16	[-0.019 – 1.349]	0.056
North America	-0.172	0.243	34	[-0.648 – 0.305]	0.480
Oceania	0.344	0.448	5	[-0.527 – 1.216]	0.438
West Europe	-0.001	0.339	24	[-0.666 – 0.664]	0.997
Children					
North America	1.400	0.644	2	[0.137 – 2.662]	0.029
West Europe	0.414	0.330	8	[-0.233 – 1.060]	0.209

For the beverage category, most OR measures (7) originated from North American case-control studies (Table 15A), with only three data points from case-control studies from Asia and Oceania. Given the few OR measures available in this category, nothing was removed. As the children population had only two ORs, the meta-analysis was conducted joining both the mixed and the children population. On average, people who consumed beverages had on average 1.350 (95% CI: 0.761 – 2.392 in Table 15B) times the odds of acquiring salmonellosis than those who did not consume those beverages. The meta-analytical funnel plot for the beverage data partition is shown in Figure 18.

Table 14B. Meta-analyses of produce consumption related pathways for *Salmonella* transmission for mixed (n=63) and children (n=10) population – Asian countries removed from the mixed population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z	
Mixed	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
		Fruits	0.082 ^a	0.251	13	[-0.411 – 0.577]	0.744
		Nuts	-0.079 ^a	0.256	6	[-0.582 – 0.428]	0.736
		Roots	-0.034 ^a	0.300	4	[-0.623 – 0.555]	0.909
		Vegetables	0.050 ^a	0.242	34	[-0.424 – 0.525]	0.835
		Veg prods	-0.103 ^a	0.261	6	[-0.615 – 0.408]	0.691
		UniOR	-0.074	0.225		[-0.516 – 0.369]	0.744
		Before 2000					0.638
	Random effects						
		s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2300	QE(df=56)		QM(df=5)	
		s ² (residual)	0.4680	p<.001		p=0.261	
		Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0002			0.294
		Points removed	1				
Children/ Infants	Fixed effects						
	MultiOR						
		Vegs/Herbs	0.693	0.464	10	[-0.216 – 1.602]	0.135
		UniOR	0.078	0.166		[-0.248 – 0.405]	0.640
		Before 2000					ND
	Random effects						
		s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2991	QE(df=8)			
		s ² (residual)	0.5609	p=0.421			
		Publication bias	-0.0004	0.0027			0.875
		Points removed	0				

ND: Not determined as all observations were from studies conducted after 2000

Figure 17. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of produce consumption pathways for *Salmonella* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table 15A. Meta-analysis of beverage consumption as risk factor for *Salmonella*-transmission by region for the combined mixed (n=8) and children (n=2) population – no region removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children					
Asia	0.479	0.935	2	[-1.353 – 2.311]	0.608
North America	0.349	0.509	7	[-0.603 – 1.392]	0.438
Oceania	0.247	1.021	1	[-1.755 – 2.249]	0.809

Table 15B. Meta-analysis of beverage consumption as risk factor for *Salmonella*-transmission for the combined mixed (n=8) and children (n=2) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
UniOR					
Any beverage	0.300	0.292	10	[-0.273 – 0.872]	0.305
Before 2000					0.696
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3524	QE(df=9)			
s^2 (residual)	0.3703	p=0.001			
Publication bias	-0.0030	0.0008			0.001
Points removed	0				

Figure 18. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of beverage consumption for *Salmonella* infection in the combined mixed and children population

Similar to the beverage category, for the composite foods category the mixed and the children population were grouped together for meta-analysis. In the analysis by region (Table 16A), it could be deduced that there were no significant difference in risk of salmonellosis associated to multi-ingredients foods between American (overall OR=1.822) and Asian (overall OR=1.761) countries while the lowest overall OR belonged to case-control studies from Oceania (overall OR=0.848). As sufficient OR measures were available for the subcategory meta-analysis, the data from Asian case-control studies were removed. Before the year 2000, the composite foods seemingly bore a higher risk of salmonellosis that in more recent times ($p=0.15$; Table 16B). The composite classes of dishes eaten by the mixed and children population (overall OR=2.036; 95% CI: 1.265 – 3.277) and fast-food (overall OR=2.036; 95% CI: 1.265 – 3.277) presented a numerically higher association with salmonellosis than sandwich (overall OR=1.964; 95% CI: 1.095 – 3.522; Table 16B), although no statistical differences could be found. Dishes and fast-foods consisted of compo, mostly eaten out, prepared at any restaurant or fast-food establishment serving local food, Italian, Chinese, Indian, and Thai food. In this meta-analysis, no influential OR was removed from the data subset; and, in addition, there was no statistical evidence of publication bias ($p=0.160$; Table 16B and Figure 19).

Table 16A. Meta-analysis of composite-food related pathways for *Salmonella* transmission by region for the combined mixed (n=79) and children (n=2) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children					
Asia	0.566	0.286	14	[0.004 – 1.127]	0.048
North America	0.600	0.208	17	[0.192 – 1.008]	0.004
North Europe	0.547	0.244	30	[0.069 – 1.026]	0.025
Oceania	-0.164	0.357	4	[-0.864 – 0.535]	0.646
West Europe	0.384	0.314	16	[-0.231 – 1.000]	0.221

Table 16B. Meta-analysis of composite-food related pathways for *Salmonella* transmission for the combined mixed (n=65) and children (n=2) population – Asian countries were removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
MultiOR					
Dishes	0.711 ^a	0.243	45	[0.235 – 1.187]	0.003
Fast-food	0.728 ^a	0.259	16	[0.235 – 1.220]	0.004
Sandwich	0.675 ^a	0.298	6	[0.091 – 1.259]	0.023
UniOR	-0.283	0.213		[-0.914 – -0.078]	0.020
Before 2000	0.397	0.277		[-0.146 – 0.941]	0.150
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2448	QE(df=62)		QM(df=3)	
s^2 (residual)	0.5889	p<.001		p=0.23	
Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.160
Points removed	0				

Figure 19. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of composite food consumption pathways for *Salmonella* infection in the combined mixed and children population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

3.1.3 Meta-analysis on the risk of *Salmonella* transmission by ready-to-eat foods and barbecued foods

North American case-control studies presented overall a very weak association between RTE foods and salmonellosis (overall OR=1.010), while case-control studies from Northern and Western Europe presented higher pooled ORs between 1.239 – 1.879 (Table 17A). Because sufficient OR data points were available, the case-control studies from Asian and South American countries were not included for the meta-analysis by subcategory.

Table 17A. Meta-analysis of the risk of *Salmonella* transmission due to consumption of RTE foods by region in the mixed (n=56) and children (n=6) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children					
Asia	0.274	0.340	7	[-0.393 – 0.941]	0.420
North America	0.010	0.235	16	[-0.451 – 0.471]	0.966
North Europe	0.631	0.303	9	[0.038 – 1.225]	0.037
South America	0.804	0.591	7	[-0.355 – 1.963]	0.174
West Europe	0.215	0.278	23	[-0.330 – 0.759]	0.440

Among the RTE subcategories (i.e., dairy-, eggs-, meat- and produce-based), there was not a single class that *statistically* differed from the other in terms of odds of acquiring salmonellosis by the combined mixed and children population (QM test, p=0.433; Table 17B). Overall, people who consumed RTE foods had 1.273 times the odds of becoming ill compared to those who did not eat RTE foods (95% CI: 0.926 – 1.747). Yet, numerically, the lowest mean ORs belonged to the salad-based RTE (overall OR=1.056; 95% CI: 0.523 – 2.136) while the highest to the dairy-based RTE (overall OR=1.409; 95% CI: 0.966 – 2.056; Table 17B).

When meta-analysed, the consumption of BBQ meats turned out to be a significant risk factor for human salmonellosis (p=0.075; Table 18). The barbecuing procedure may be prone to undercooking and cross-contamination. People who consumed BBQ meats had overall 2.065 times the odds of acquiring salmonellosis than those who were not exposed to BBQ meats (95% CI: 0.931 – 4.581). In the meta-analyses performed on the RTE and BBQ foods, there did not appear to be strong graphical evidence of publication bias (Figure 20), which was statistically confirmed by the absence of association between study size and the reported ORs (p=0.525 in Table 17 and p=0.832 in Table 18).

Table 17B. Meta-analysis of the risk of *Salmonella* transmission due to consumption of RTE foods overall and by food category in the mixed (n=43) and children (n=5) population. Asian and South American countries removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All RTE foods	0.241	0.162	48	[-0.076 – 0.558]	0.136
Fixed effects					
Dairy-based	0.343 ^a	0.193	17	[-0.034 – 0.721]	0.075
Eggs-based	0.209 ^a	0.378	3	[-0.532 – 0.951]	0.579
Meat-based	0.233 ^a	0.187	23	[-0.134 – 0.600]	0.213
Produce-based	0.055 ^a	0.359	5	[-0.648 – 0.759]	0.878
Before 2000					0.186
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3990	QE(df=44)		QM(df=4)	
s^2 (residual)	0.7320	p<.001		p=0.433	
Publication bias	-0.0000	-0.0000			0.525
Points removed	0				

Table 18. Meta-analysis of the risk of *Salmonella* transmission due to consumption of BBQ meats by the mixed population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
BBQ meats	0.725	0.406	7	[-0.072 – 1.522]	0.075
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.4434	QE(df=6)			
s^2 (residual)	0.6696	p=0.014			
Publication bias	0.0003	0.0013			0.832
Points removed	0				

Figure 20. Funnel plots of the meta-analysis of RTE foods (left) and BBQ meats (right) as risk factors for *Salmonella* infection. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

In order to get a comprehensive view of the results of all meta-analyses on the various data partitions (namely, host-specific factors, travel-related, environmental pathways, animal pathways and food pathways by category and population type), the overall ORs were graphically assembled into forest plots. Figures 21 and 22 compile the disaggregated host-specific factors and pathways of exposure with their corresponding pooled ORs in decreasing order. Figure 21 shows those whose overall ORs were higher than 2.0 while Figure 22 those whose overall ORs were lower than 2.0. According to this meta-analysis study, key determinants of disease, having mean ORs higher than 3.0, were: contact with farm animals in the children population, recent use of antibiotics in the mixed population, travel, person-to-person transmission in children, playground in children, chronic diseases in the mixed population, use of anti-acids in children, attendance to day care in children, contaminated drink water in children, pork meat in children, and contact with pets and wild animals by children. Generally speaking, in the mixed population, salmonellosis had a stronger association with environmental routes than with animal contact, except for occupational exposure. After host-specific and environmental factors, salmonellosis was highly associated with the consumption of some food groups. Food pathways whose pooled ORs were higher than 1.50, in decreasing order, were: egg products in the mixed population, minced beef in children, pork in the mixed population, red meats other than beef in the mixed population, milk powder in infants, eggs in the mixed population, poultry in the mixed population, fast-food, BBQ meats in the mixed population, multi-ingredient dishes, fresh vegetables in children, multi-ingredient sandwiches, processed meats, seafood in children and beef in the mixed population (Figure 21). Foodstuffs that on meta-analysis had weak or non-significant association with salmonellosis in the mixed population were the different classes of produce, dairy-origin fats, processed fish, cheese, milk and fish (Figure 22). Breastfeeding was demonstrated to protect infants against infection with salmonellosis, as on average, breastfed infants had 3.5 times lower probability of acquiring the disease than those who were not breastfed.

Figure 21. Forest plot of the overall odds-ratios of acquiring salmonellosis for host-specific factors, travel, environmental, animal and food pathways by category and population type (mixed and children), ranked in decreasing order

Figure 22. Forest plot of the overall odds-ratios of acquiring salmonellosis for host-specific factors, environmental, animal and food pathways by category and population type (mixed and children), ranked in decreasing order (sequence of Figure 21)

3.1.4 *Meta-analysis on the effects of handling and setting on the risk of Salmonella transmission by food consumption*

From the meta-analytical data, it was possible to estimate, for some classes, how the overall OR (*base OR*) was affected by mishandling of food (i.e., eating raw, undercooked or unwashed) or by eating food prepared outside the home (i.e., eating out as setting). The exponential of the parameters β_{2m} and β_{3n} from Equation (5) can be interpreted as the number of times mishandling food or eating out, respectively, could on average increase the base OR. This is because, in mathematical terms, the ratio of the mean OR when food is mishandled (or, alternatively, when food is eaten out) to the base OR is defined by the estimate “ $\frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_{2m})}{\exp(\beta_0)} = \exp(\beta_{2m})$ ” for handling or “ $\frac{\exp(\beta_0 + \beta_{3n})}{\exp(\beta_0)} = \exp(\beta_{3n})$ ” for setting. The results of the effects of eating out and handling in contrast to their base OR are shown in Table 19 by food classes.

Eating undercooked pork represents a significant increase of the base OR (1.115) of acquiring salmonellosis by 3.769 times (95% CI: 2.148 – 6.183) whereas eating pork prepared outside the home can also increase the odds by a comparable factor (3.785; 95% CI: 1.795 – 7.086). The odds of contracting salmonellosis from eating poultry could increase by ~2.7 (95% CI: 1.254 – 5.103) if it was not fully cooked. Eating poultry prepared at establishments has been found to increase the base OR by a factor of 1.801 (95% CI: 1.444 – 2.223). People who consumed *undercooked* eggs presented overall 1.248 (95% CI: 1.053 – 1.469) times the odds of becoming ill than those who *simply* consumed eggs, whereas for those who consumed *raw* eggs the OR increased by a higher factor of 1.884 (95% CI: 1.283 – 2.665). Eating any kind of egg preparation outside the home also increased the odds of acquiring the disease by 1.583 (95% CI: 1.167 – 2.104). Likewise, having undercooked beef and undercooked processed meat also increased the risk of disease by 1.507 (95% CI: 0.936 – 2.298) and 1.468 (95% CI: 0.858 – 2.359), respectively; although these factors were lower than those observed for undercooked pork and poultry. When beef and processed meats were prepared outside the home, the base OR increased by 1.802 (95% CI: 0.707 – 3.797) and 1.685 (95% CI: 1.074 – 2.521), respectively. The meta-analyses demonstrated that undercooking was not the only risky food preparation habit, but also improper washing. People who consumed vegetables *without previous proper washing* had 1.447 (95% CI: 0.882 – 2.243) times the odds of becoming infected with salmonellosis than those who *simply* consumed vegetables. In addition, the consumption of unpasteurised milk or cheese made of raw milk increased the base OR by a factor of 1.373 (95% CI: 0.878 – 2.036). The full results of Equation (5) fitted to each of the above food classes are shown in the supplementary Tables S1-S7 with their respective funnel plots (Figure S1-S7). In general, the funnel plots built for the meta-analyses of the overall effects of handling and setting appeared well-behaved; the spread of observations did not hint an evident presence of publication bias.

3.1.5 *Synthesis of the risks associated to ways of preparation and poor handling of foods*

The relative importance of the risk factors associated with poor handling of foods is shown in Figure 23 by means of a forest plot of their ORs in decreasing order. The most risky handling practices were linked to cross-contamination and inadequate storage, namely: not washing hands regularly; poor handling of raw eggs; not adequately cleaning chopping board between raw meat and non-meat items or cleaning chopping board with water only; not disinfecting

dish clothes; storing eggs at room temperature or keeping them longer than 3 weeks; keeping cooked meats more than one hour at room temperature; and using the same knife for raw and cooked food. The last four odds of disease for the children population at the bottom of the forest plot (Figure 23) arise from poor food handling practised by the parents at home or those responsible for food preparation.

Table 19. Meta-analysed effects of handling and setting on base ORs by relevant food class

Food class	Estimate	Mean	2.5 th percentile	97.5 th percentile
Pork	OR(Base)	1.115	0.515	2.104
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	3.769	2.148	6.183
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	3.785	1.795	7.086
Poultry	OR(Base)	1.463	1.092	1.920
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	2.699	1.254	5.103
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	1.801	1.444	2.223
Eggs	OR(Base)	1.825	1.122	2.815
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	1.884	1.283	2.665
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	1.248	1.053	1.469
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	1.583	1.167	2.104
Beef	OR(Base)	1.479	0.740	2.658
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	1.507	0.936	2.298
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	1.802	0.707	3.797
Processed meat	OR(Base)	1.327	0.843	2.003
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	1.468	0.858	2.359
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	1.685	1.074	2.521
Vegetables	OR(Base)	1.222	0.846	1.705
	OR(Unwashed)/OR(Base)	1.447	0.882	2.243
Milk and cheese	OR(Base)	0.819	0.660	1.003
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	1.373	0.878	2.037

With regards to food preparation, some common practices can turn into important pathways of exposure to salmonellosis (Figure 24). Handling frozen chicken (OR=5.00), raw pieces of chicken (OR=1.02-2.50), raw whole chicken (OR=1.30-1.60), and thawing chicken (OR=2.38-2.55) and other meats in water (OR=1.10) were significantly associated with salmonellosis in the mixed population. Other important sources of cross-contamination during food preparation were found to be: wiping dishes dry (OR=1.60), having more than one person at a time preparing the meal (OR=1.60) and use of wooden chopping boards as opposed to glass-made (OR=1.30). The simple procedures of food preparation by parents, such as having raw meats in the kitchen (OR=2.60-5.31) constitute significant pathways of

exposure for their children. Parents who store eggs for more than two weeks (OR=3.60-3.80) or prepare undercooked meat at home (OR=4.00) increase the odds of their children to acquire salmonellosis (Figure 24).

Figure 23. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring salmonellosis associated to poor food handling practices

Figure 24. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring salmonellosis associated to food preparation practices

4 Conclusions

4.1 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic salmonellosis

- ❖ The most important risk factors for transmission of salmonellosis in the mixed population is international travel (OR=4.17) and use of antibiotics (OR=5.18).
- ❖ In children, the most important routes of transmission are contact with farm animals (OR=5.98) and contagion through person-to-person (OR=4.00), playground (OR=3.65) and attendance to day care (OR=3.31), as well as recent use of anti-acids (OR=3.35) and contaminated drinking water (OR=3.25).
- ❖ Breastfed infants have on average 3.5 times lower odds of acquiring the disease than those who are not breastfed.
- ❖ As a whole, the host-specific factors (antibiotics, chronic diseases, anti-acids) and some environmental/animal routes (drink water, recreational water, occupational exposure and children's contact with animals) bear more risk of transmission than food consumption.
- ❖ Within the food vehicles of transmission, key determinants of disease in children are: pork meat (OR=3.19), minced beef (OR =2.78), milk and infant formula (OR=2.30), fresh vegetables (OR=2.00) and processed meats (OR=1.84).
- ❖ In the mixed population, the most important food routes of salmonellosis are: egg products (OR=2.91), pork meat (OR=2.66), red meats other than beef (OR=2.44), eggs (OR=2.11) and poultry meat (OR=2.11).
- ❖ Composite foods such as non-RTE dishes (OR=2.04), non-RTE sandwiches (OR=1.96) and fast-food (OR=2.07) bear greater association with salmonellosis than RTE foods (OR=1.27).
- ❖ People who stated having eaten undercooked pork, poultry or beef increase their odds of becoming infected with salmonellosis by 1.5 – 3.8 than those who recalled having eaten simply pork.
- ❖ People who ate pork, poultry, beef, eggs or processed meat prepared outside home have their odds of acquiring salmonellosis increased by 1.8-3.8. Hence, in general, eating food prepared in establishments is an important risk factor by itself.
- ❖ People who consumed undercooked eggs presented overall 1.25 times the odds of becoming ill than those who consumed eggs, whereas for those who consumed raw eggs the mean base OR increased by a higher factor of 1.88.

- ❖ Not properly washing vegetables before consumption increased the odds of salmonellosis by 1.45 while the consumption of raw milk and raw milk cheese increase the odds of disease by 1.37.
- ❖ Foodstuffs that on meta-analysis have weak or non-significant association with salmonellosis in the mixed population are: vegetables, roots, nuts, vegetable products, dairy-origin fats, processed fish, cheese, milk and fish.

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APPENDIX

1 Supplementary tables and figures for *Salmonella* spp.

Table S1. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of poultry (n=103)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Multi					
Handl & Setting: Base	0.369	0.144		[0.087 – 0.652]	0.010
Handl: Undercooked	0.933	0.356	9	[0.235 – 1.631]	0.009
Setting: Eating out	0.582	0.111	25	[0.364 – 0.799]	<.0001
Uni	-0.248	0.137		[-0.516 – 0.020]	0.069
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1639	QE(df=97)			
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0113	p<.001			
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0019				
s^2 (residual)	0.5939				
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000			0.0121
Points removed	2				

Figure S1. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of poultry. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S2. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of processed meat (n=63)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Multi					
Handl & Setting: Base	0.259	0.221		[-0.175 – 0.693]	0.242
Handl: Raw or undercoo	0.351	0.258	10	[-0.154 – 0.856]	0.173
Setting: Eating out	0.497	0.218	14	[0.070 – 0.924]	0.022
Uni	-0.115	0.174		[-0.456 – 0.227]	0.511
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3346	QE(df=57)			
s^2 (residual)	0.7061	p<.001			
Publication bias	-0.0001	0.0000			0.308
Points removed	2				

Figure S2. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of processed meat. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S3. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of beef (n=37)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Multi					
Handl & Setting: Base	0.338	0.325		[-0.300 – 0.975]	0.298
Handl: Raw or undercook	0.382	0.230	9	[-0.069 – 0.833]	0.097
Setting: Eating out	0.496	0.429	5	[-0.344 – 1.337]	0.247
Uni	-0.346	0.328		[-0.990 – 0.298]	0.292
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3214	QE(df=33)			
s^2 (residual)	0.5386	p<.001			
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0002			0.266
Points removed	1				

Figure S3. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of poultry. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S4. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of eggs (n=143)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Multi					
Handl & Setting: Base	0.574	0.234		[0.114 – 1.033]	0.014
Handl: Raw	0.616	0.186	13	[0.251 – 0.981]	0.001
Handl: Undercooked	0.218	0.085	49	[0.051– 0.386]	0.011
Setting: Eating out	0.448	0.150	30	[0.154 – 0.743]	0.003
Setting: Home	-0.046	0.136	13	[-0.312 – 0.219]	0.731
Uni	-0.317	0.216		[-0.740 – 0.107]	0.143
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1878	QE(df=133)			
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.0748	p<.001			
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0006				
s^2 (residual)	0.8327				
Publication bias	-0.0000	0.0000			0.6039
Points removed	4				

Figure S4. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of eggs. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S5. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of pork meat (n=23)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Multi					
Handl & Setting: Base	0.043	0.359		[-0.662 – 0.748]	0.119
Handl: Undercooked	1.282	0.270	12	[0.752 – 1.811]	<.0001
Setting: Eating out	1.270	0.349	3	[0.586 – 1.955]	<.0001
Uni	-0.248	0.309		[-0.854 – 0.359]	0.424
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1043	QE(df=19)			
s^2_{v2} (Multi OR)	0.1309	p=0.015			
s^2_{v1} (Uni OR)	0.0049				
s^2 (residual)	0.3972				
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0002			0.269
Points removed	0				

Figure S5. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of pork meat

Table S6. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of vegetables (n=48)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Multi					
Handl: Base	0.184	0.179		[-0.167 – 0.535]	0.306
Handl: Raw	-0.162	0.137	10	[-0.431 – 0.107]	0.239
Handl: Unwashed	0.342	0.238	4	[-0.126 – 0.808]	0.152
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3892	QE(df=44)			
s^2 (residual)	0.4224	p<.001			
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0002			0.282
Points removed	1				

Figure S6. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of vegetables. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S7. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of milk and cheese (n=26)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Handl: Base	-0.206	0.107		[-0.416 – 0.005]	0.050
Handl: Raw	0.295	0.213	8	[-0.122 – 0.713]	0.166
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0350	QE(df=23)			
s^2 (residual)	0.2056	p=0.179			
Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0000			<.0001
Points removed	1				

Figure S7. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling on the risk of salmonellosis by consumption of milk and cheese. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias